

SUPSI

**BEIRUT, SURSOCK PALACE
EMERGENCY MEASURES ON PLASTER DECORATIONS**

REPORT SUMMER SCHOOL 2022

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BEIRUT, SURSOCK PALACE EMERGENCY MEASURES ON PLASTER DECORATIONS

SUMMER SCHOOL 2022, EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The second SUPSI mission, which took place from June 6th to July 8th 2022, had a twofold objective: to secure very unstable areas of the ground floor in order to avoid further losses of the original material and to organize an educational worksite involving Swiss and Lebanese students. This mission was carried out within the “Conservation of Beirut cultural heritage and post-disaster recovery” research project funded by the State Secretary for Education, Research and Innovation SEFRI (LHMENA) with additional financial support from the RestArt Beirut Foundation and the Swiss Embassy in Lebanon.

The aim of the summer school was to train students in planning and implementing emergency measures to secure delicate and unstable plaster decorations at risk of falling. During the five-week program, on-site practice was sided by theoretical lectures to provide basic information about the context, treatment procedures and a methodological road-map to plan and execute conservation-restoration interventions.

In agreement with the owners, operations were focused on the ceiling and walls of the central hall – because of their relevant architectural quality – and on the south part of the gallery and the vestibule. The choice was to leave the northern areas untouched, as they will be addressed in the coming months, during the structural consolidation of the façade.

The first operation conducted on site was aimed at understanding the characteristics of the building structure and the deterioration phenomena on the surfaces from a closer point of view with the use of two mobile scaffoldings. During the first condition assessment these are could not be seen close up.

The interventions were divided between temporary and permanent measures, based on the following criteria: prioritize permanent solutions over temporary fixings; pursue minimal intervention; not hinder future interventions to be performed on the surfaces; seek reversibility by choosing solutions that could be easily removed if needed; find solutions that could be realized in a short time frame in order to remove the security nets as much as possible.

The interventions on the plaster decorations in Sursock Palace included the following operations: facing, securing, pinning, edging repair, re-adhesion of previously detached elements and building of new anchoring systems.

At the end of this second mission, indications of urgent needs (securing the ceiling of the main hall) and future interventions were shared and discussed with arch. Kallas and are described in detail, together with each operation, in the following final report that will be delivered by SUPSI to all partners involved in the project. The ceiling in the main hall deserves immediate attention since it showed a strong weakness of the Baghdadi structure of the perimeter, which is at high risk of falling, hence not fit for use until taken care of. The owners were therefore invited to intervene with the utmost urgency with its structural consolidation and to put back in place the protective nets.

For the future, other initiatives should be considered to promote the fruitful collaboration between stakeholders in order to continue the work begun so far in practical and methodological training for the conservation of the decorated surfaces.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1.	INTRODUCTION	3
2.	SUMMER SCHOOL DESCRIPTION	4
3.	MATERIALS AND EXECUTION TECHNIQUES	6
	3.1. Ceilings.....	6
	3.2. Plaster decorations.....	7
4.	CONDITION ASSESSMENT	8
5.	EMERGENCY TREATMENT	9
	5.1. Criteria	9
	5.2. Types of interventions	9
6.	MAIN HALL (1.5B).....	11
	6.1. Walls execution techniques.....	11
	6.2. Walls condition assessment.....	13
	6.3. Walls Summer school treatments	15
	6.3.1. Trials for Phase 2	17
	6.3.2. Future treatments (Phase 2)	23
	6.4. Ceiling execution techniques	23
	6.5. Ceiling condition assessment.....	25
	6.6. Ceiling Summer school treatments	27
	6.6.1. Trials for Phase 2	29
	6.6.2. Future treatments (Phase 2)	30
7.	SOUTH GALLERY (ROOM 1.5C)	31
	7.1. Execution techniques	31
	7.2. Condition assessment	32
	7.3. Summer school treatments	34
	7.3.1. Phase 1.2	34
	7.3.2. Trials for Phase 2	36
	7.3.3. Future treatments (Phase 2)	37
8.	VESTIBULE (ROOM 1.9).....	39
	8.1. Execution techniques	39
	8.2. Condition assessment.....	40
	8.3. Summer school treatments	42
	8.3.1. Phase 1.2	42
	8.3.2. Future treatments (Phase 2)	44
9.	CONCLUSIONS	45
10.	FURTHER STEPS.....	46
11.	REFERENCES.....	47
12.	ANNEXES	47
	12.1. Materials inventory	47
	12.2. CAD drawings	47
	12.3. Material technical sheets.....	47

1. INTRODUCTION

The first mission to Beirut (carried out by G. Jean, G. Nicoli, and G. Russo in September 2021) aimed at assessing the state of conservation of the plaster decorations of Sursock Palace providing essential data for defining the priorities of intervention and planning future steps in collaboration with the owners and RestART Beirut.

As a result, two phases of intervention were advised:

Phase 1: Emergency interventions to be carried out before starting the work on the architectural structure divided in:

- *Phase 1.1:* securing the endangered areas to allow people to work safely in the internal spaces;
- *Phase 1.2:* carrying out urgent intervention to secure and avoid further losses of the delicate and unstable decorations.

Phase 2: Conservation treatment of the plaster decorations to be carried out after the work on the architectural structure (such as pre-consolidation, consolidation, cleaning, filling of missing parts, reconstruction and retouching).

These measures, suggested the collaboration of:

- construction workers and carpenters to prop the counter ceilings on the second floor and to remove unstable parts already partially detached from the support, and
- conservator-restorers for the decorated plaster elements to be preserved.

In spring 2022, under the direction of arch. Joe Kallas, the architectural elements were secured by:

- propping of the ceilings of the staircase and of the wooden ribs supporting the decorated ceilings of the central hall and room 2.3 on the first floor (Fig.1);
- installation of metal nets under the vault's impost frame of the ground floor rooms to prevent falling of plaster fragments from hitting people using these rooms (Fig.2, Fig.3).

Fig.1_Proping of the ceiling, central hall, first floor

Fig.2_Installation of metal nets, ceilings of the ground floor rooms

Fig.3_Decorated plaster elements fallen from the ceiling on the metal net

2. SUMMER SCHOOL DESCRIPTION

A second SUPSI mission took place from June 6th to July 8th 2022 with a twofold objective:

- to secure very unstable areas of the ground floor (Phase 1.2);
- to organize an educational worksite involving Swiss and Lebanese students.

This mission was carried out within the “Conservation of Beirut cultural heritage and post-disaster recovery” research project funded by the State Secretary for Education, Research and Innovation SEFRI (LHMENA) with additional financial support from the RestArt Beirut Foundation and the Swiss Embassy in Lebanon.

The students involved [Christina Bitar (USEK), Elise El Rassi (USEK), Filippo Gabutti (SUPSI), Sara Haddad (freelancer), Gaia Iacobucci (SUPSI), Karl Kassouf (USEK), Prisca Leoni (SUPSI) and Francesca Paola Luciani (USEK)] worked under the direction of SUPSI lecturers Giovanni Nicoli and Giulia Russo.

The aim of the summer school was to train students in planning and implementing emergency measures to secure delicate and unstable plaster decorations at risk of falling.

As requested by the owners, it was decided not to intervene on the rooms on the north side of the building on which structural consolidation work was already planned. Instead, operations were focused on the ceiling and walls of the central hall – because of their relevant architectural quality – and on the south part of the gallery and the vestibule (Fig.4).

Unlike the first mission where the surfaces could only be assessed from the ground, in this occasion two mobile scaffoldings enabled the team to reach even the higher decorated areas. Therefore, the first operation conducted in the field was aimed at understanding the characteristics of the building structure and the deterioration phenomena on the surfaces from a closer point of view (Fig.5 – Fig.8).

Graphic documentation was done starting from the orthophotos delivered by arch. Kallas’ photogrammetry of the rooms and detailed photographic documentation was carried out during the entire period. The mappings were then digitized creating thematic drawings showing execution techniques, state of conservation and interventions done during the summer school (Fig.9, Fig.10).

Fig.4_Summer School 2022 working area

During the five-week program, on-site practice was sided by the following theoretical lectures to provide students with basic information about the context, treatment procedures and a methodological road-map about the process to plan and execute conservation-restoration interventions:

- Description of Sursock Palace's history, context, and study of the materials' architecture by Joe Kallas;
- The role of documentation on site (graphic and photographic documentation, glossaries and data management) by Giulia Russo;
- The definition of intervention criteria by Giovanni Nicoli;
- Emergency treatments description and case studies by Alberto Felici (online) SUPSI lecturer;
- Choice of materials and intervention phases by Giovanni Nicoli;
- Site visit of St. George Greek Orthodox cathedral and discussion on wall paintings' conservation treatments with Yasmine Makaroun and Caterina Michelini Tocci.

Fig.5_ Removal of safety nets room 1.5b

Fig.6_ Main hall's condition assessment

Fig.7_ Study of the execution technique

Fig.8_ Mapping of conditions of the main hall's panels

Fig.10_ Mapping digitization in AutoCAD

Fig.9_ St. George visit with Y. Makaroun and C. Michelini Tocci

3. MATERIALS AND EXECUTION TECHNIQUES

Being inspired by European bourgeois palaces, Sursock Palace is a more elaborated version of the *Beirut central hall house*, typical beirut architecture of the second half of the XIX century. Despite the similarity to buildings found also in Europe, the publication *Houses of Beirut 1860-1925. Restoration manual* by N. Chahine and F. Dagher has been a helpful resource for the description of the local construction methods.

3.1. Ceilings

The ceilings of the ground floor level are made following the flat jack arch slab system to cover larger areas and to have a more resistant slab rather than the traditional timber flat ceiling.

Hidden by the plaster layer, the structure is composed by steel I-beams aligned at intervals of 40 to 60 cm, filled with sandstone blocks/lime and connected by steel tie-rods generating pressure from the top. The painted plaster and stucco decorative elements are applied directly on the jack arch slab (Fig.11, Fig.12).

Fig. 11_Typical section of a Beirut jack arch slab (BHI 2021)

Fig. 12_Visible jack arch slab structure from the ceiling's lost decoration of gallery 2.5c on the first floor

In addition, the ceilings of the gallery and the main hall consist in a hybrid solution between the previous technique and the so-called Baghdadi technique. Respectively, the structure of the coves in the gallery and of the perimeter ceiling in the main hall is composed of wooden laths nailed on wooden ribs and joists on which a layer of gypsum is applied. A good key between the laths and the plaster held the decoration in place (Fig. 13, Fig. 14).

Fig. 13_Typical section of a painted Baghdadi ceiling (BHI 2021)

Fig. 14_Perimeter cornice structure, Main hall

3.2. Plaster decorations

The decorations of Sursock Palace are made of a gypsum-based plaster [calcium sulfate hemihydrate ($\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot \frac{1}{2} \text{H}_2\text{O}$)]. The characteristics of this material are deeply influenced by the following factors: the quantity of water added in the mixture, the water's temperature, and the method of mixing. Consequently, we assume that the execution of casted elements was achieved with less water and longer mixing time due to the lack of shrinkage, the rapid setting-time and the regular crystallization of the material. Instead, the decorations that required more workmanship were made using more water in the mixture and less mixing time.

The decorative elements of the rooms can be divided in two main categories based on the type of execution but also according to their type of modeling.

Elements modelled **on site**:

- modelled by running molds: usually the element/cornice follows the defects of the surface (easier to detect on a non-planar surface when the element follows its deformation)
- modelled by free hand: recognizable in sophisticated and irregular decorated areas when the process of making requires good manual skills.

Elements modelled **on the bench**:

- *casted*: a recurring module and joints in repetitive decorations could be found.
- *modelled by running molds*: same as casted elements.
- *modelled by free hand*: the element can be modelled from scratch or, sometimes, can be a hybrid solution starting from a casted element which is later engraved when gypsum is still wet (engraved either on the bench or directly on site).

All elements modelled on the bench were later set on the surface using a layer of gypsum that acted as a sort of adhesive. No original pin or anchoring system was found in the plaster decorations to ameliorate the connection of these elements to the support.

These elements can be easily recognized when they're missing because what remains after their detachment is their negative imprint on the surface. (Fig.15, Fig.16).

Fig. 15_ West gallery adjacent to main hall ground floor, missing casted elements

Fig. 16_Detail of missing casted elements, keying signs on the surface

4. CONDITION ASSESSMENT

The explosion of August 2020 strongly damaged the palace but also highlighted some intrinsic weaknesses of the plaster decorations due to both the execution technique and previous deterioration phenomena. The lack of any sort of anchoring system in the making of these decorations, puts them at risk of detaching. This phenomenon is particularly dangerous as it could happen also in an immediate and unattended way. **It is very important to emphasize how elements that look stable can be on the verge of imminent fall.**

The mapping of the conditions was tackling only the phenomena to be addressed during this phase of intervention and no other issues (as flaking for example or dirt deposits), namely:

- *Crack*: a discontinuity in the stratigraphy resulting in a visible separation of one part from another (Fig.17);
- *Detachment*: a discontinuity between one or more layers of the stratigraphy which generally leads to the layers fall. Detected by acoustic tracing: hollow areas are checked and eventually located by knocking the surface (Fig.18);
- *Partial loss*: material loss of a layer/part (Fig.19);
- *Total loss*: missing part that affects the integrity of the element (Fig.20);
- *Areas at risk of detachment (in need of securing intervention)*: areas affected by intrinsic weakness and potentially unstable.

Fig.17_Crack

Fig.18_Detachment

Fig.19_Partial loss

Fig.20_Total loss

5. EMERGENCY TREATMENT

Emergency measures are considered treatments that aim at stabilizing an active deterioration until a more definitive intervention can be carried out. During the condition assessment, detached elements that proved to be very unstable and that could endanger people's safety were removed and either disposed (if plaster debris) or collected for future remounting. The intervention was therefore divided between temporary measures and permanent measures.

5.1. Criteria

Since temporary emergency treatments can remain for longer periods of time before permanent conservation treatment can be achieved (Leitner 2000), in the planning of the interventions it was fundamental to set the following guiding criteria:

- Pursue minimal intervention considering the effectiveness of the measure, limiting the intervention to the strictly needed treatment, and its minimal visual impact;
- Not hinder future interventions to be performed on the surfaces (Phase 2);
- Seek reversibility by choosing solutions that could be easily removed if needed;
- Prioritize permanent solutions over temporary fixings;
- Find solutions that could be realized in a short time frame in order to remove the security nets as much as possible;

The selection of the materials and products used during the intervention considered their compatibility with original materials and techniques. In the future, other materials (with the same properties) could be used in case of availability problems (warehouse storage, different branding, cost, etc).

5.2. Types of interventions

The interventions on the plaster decorations in Sursock Palace included the following operations (Leitner 2000):

- **Facing:** temporary procedure to secure an element from falling by adhering a surface reinforcement to a safer area with a reversible adhesive.

Structural role: connecting endangered areas to structurally stable areas. Intended to be temporary.

Materials: gauzes, adhesive [an acrylic resin (Paraloid B72) and a methylhydroxycellulose (Tylose MH 300 P)]

Application technology: choose the adhesive based on the surface characteristics, apply it by brush on the gauze and apply pressure on the surface. Some plaster decorations were also secured without using adhesive but only gauze and nails taking advantage of the behind wooden structure.

Notes: The choice of the adhesive depended on multiple factors such as the type of surface's finishing layer, the product's time of setting according to the needs of the following phase of intervention and the extent of the facing area (considering its removal). Paraloid B72, a common acrylic resin used in conservation, was preferred for quick adhesions interventions and where the use of its removal solvent (Acetone) would not compromise the decoration's finishing layer. Indeed, the surfaces decorated by gildings and varnishes were stabilized with Tylose MH300P (methylhydroxycellulose) which guarantees adhesion also at low percentages and is water-soluble. This product was also used in more extended areas (panels) preferring the use of water rather than the solvent for its removal.

- **Pinning:** secure in position unstable or detached sections (renders, wood, etc.) by temporary or long-term anchoring systems.

Structural role: connecting unstable or detached sections to the support seeking stability.

Materials: nails, screws, plates, washers, fiberglass, steel bars, gauze, adhesive plaster compatible with gypsum as a cellulose strengthened binder (Polyfilla).

Application technology: depending on the execution technique and the weight of the decorations it was proceeded according to different application technologies:

Masonry as support

- Pinning with rawlplug: for punctual fixing
- Pinning with rawlplug and washer: to spread the force on a larger area
- Pinning with screw, Polyfilla and cotton: Polyfilla was added in order to create some additional supporting bridge in the anchoring system
- Pinning with screw, washer, Polyfilla and cotton: same as above but using the washer to spread the force on a larger area
- Chemical anchoring: permanent fixing with the use of a bicomponent reaction resin mortar (polyester Wurth WIT-PM 200) and a metal pin (screw or steel bar). This intervention was carried out in cases where the support could not be considered homogeneously sound, and the resin could act both as a filler and as an additional support to the pin.

Wood as support

- Pinning with screw: for punctual fixing using screws with different lengths depending on the chosen depth of anchoring (9 cm or 15 cm)
- Pinning with screw and washer: to spread the force on a larger area

Notes: The following materials were selected for this phase of intervention based on their mechanical properties, their durability and the repeatability of the intervention:

- *Pins:* flat head nails (different sizes and lengths), countersunk wood screw, bugle-head torx screw, rawlplugs, galvanized steel wire, 60mm reinforced 30% fiberglass washers, plates;
- *Rods:* fiberglass rods, threaded galvanized steel rod;
- *Fabrics:* stretch gauze bandage rolls, bandages, jutes fibers, multiaxial fiberglass fabric;
- *Resin:* Wurth WIT-PM 200, polyester resin.

- **Edging repair:** application of a layer of plaster to protect and stabilize exposed plaster edges from loss, and dirt infiltration.

Structural role: connecting endangered areas to structurally stable areas and preventing detachment.

Materials: adhesive plaster compatible with gypsum (Polyfilla)

Application technology: apply the plaster layer with a spatula connecting the level of the plaster with the missing part.

Notes: Polyfilla was used throughout the entire summer school treatment for its high compatibility with gypsum, its strength (being a cellulose-reinforced binder) and its workability. Indeed, only a small amount of water is required (only in the mixing phase), and it is a shrinkage-free material.

6. MAIN HALL (1.5B)

The main hall is a rectangular space with 4 sides 3-arched opening towards the surrounding gallery. The plaster decoration of the room, proceeding from bottom to top, consists of four panels at the corners, the arches' cornices, the flat fascia (east and south walls), the medallions, the coffered ceiling. (Fig.21 – Fig.24).

Fig.21_Main hall before the blast in 2019
(ph. Ferranti)

Fig.22_Main hall after the blast in 2021
(ANSA)

Fig.23_Main hall before the blast (ph. Guillaume de Lautier)

Fig.24_Main hall after the blast (ph. Alex Cochrane)

6.1. Walls execution techniques

The panels at the corners (put in place by the grandmother of the owner at the beginning of the '900) are made by the assembling of different elements, all interlocked between each other and without using any anchoring system. Most of them are casted, starting from the four squares in the center of the decoration and the plane boards around them. The details that testify the process of plaster casting are fibers inserted in the core to add more elasticity to the structure (Fig.25) and air bubble imprints related to the pouring of gypsum in the mold (Fig.26).

The outer perimeter's decorated boards are both casted and engraved by hand. Signs of this hybrid technique are the air bubbles imprints at the edges of the incision proving the engraving tool's motion while the gypsum was still wet (Fig.27). The more protruding details were usually achieved by removing previously casted extra material, starting from a regular shape to be later engraved (Fig.28 – Fig.30).

The irregularities of the beads on top of the decoration prove that they were modelled by hand on site (Fig.31, Fig.32). Bronze gilding finishes the decoration of these elements.

The upper part of the walls is all decorated with elements made on the bench: the arches' cornices and the medallions were cast, and the flat fascia was modelled with running molds, later applied on the surface with gypsum (only the round ends were modelled with the hybrid technique) (Fig.33 – Fig.35).

Fig.25_Fibers in the core

Fig.26_Air bubbles imprints

Fig.27_Hybrid technique

Fig.28_Engraving scheme

Fig.29_Detail of the protruding part

Fig.30_Engraving scheme

Fig.31_Beads modelled by hand

Fig.32_Detail of medallion's beads

Fig.33_Fibers in flat fascia's core

Fig.34_Decoration of the east wall

Fig.35_Detail of the joints of the decorative band, east wall.

6.2. Walls condition assessment

The blast heavily damaged the plaster decorations of the room, mainly causing detachments that either led to the loss of original material (in the upper part of the walls) or the displacement of elements due to the suction effect created by the air movement that passed through the hall inward (north to south, coming from the outside) and then outward (south to north, from the inside) (Fig.36 – Fig.46).

The hollow sounds assessed during the knocking test were mainly related to the execution technique but weaknesses due to the lack of anchoring systems were observed in all the decorations, particularly in those protruding which could not rely on the support of other elements (the flat fascia and the medallions). Nails put to strengthen the panels are now corroded (Fig.41).

Fig.36_Panel 4 detachment, Main hall

Fig.37_Detachment detail, panel 4

Fig.38_Displacement of the panel

Fig.39_Flat fascia loss

Fig.40_Crack along medallion

Fig.41_Previous intervention, nail

Fig.42_Decoration of the east wall after the blast

Fig.43_Decoration of the east wall after the removal of unstable elements (Phase 1.1).

Fig.44_Panel 4 before treatment.

Fig.45_Mapping of execution techniques: Panel 4 (1.5b): in green **casted elements**, in red **casted elements modelled by free hand (hybrid technique)**, in orange **elements modelled on site by free hand**.

Fig.46_Mapping of conditions: gallery (1.5c): in green **cracks**, in blue **detachments**, in orange **partial loss**, in red **total loss**, in magenta **areas at risk of detachment**.

6.3. Walls Summer school treatments

Temporary stabilization of the panels and walls:

- Facing with gauze and adhesive (Tylose MH300 P 4% in water) the unstable areas (Fig.47 – Fig.49);
- Pinning with screw, washer, Polyfilla and cotton the unstable elements to fix them to the masonry. This operation was carried out by (Fig.50 – Fig.52):
 - 1) choosing the area to drill by finding the compromise between the best working conditions for the pin and how easily the intervention could be hidden in the future;
 - 2) drilling an angled hole to create a more effective key for the pin;
 - 3) measuring the depth of the hole (1,5 cm deeper than the screw's length);
 - 4) cleaning the holes from dust and debris;
 - 5) building the pin by using a washer, some gauze (to protect the decorated surface) and a screw;
 - 6) wrapping cotton at the end of the screw and adding Polyfilla on it;
 - 7) inserting the pin.
- Edging repair of wall's plaster missing parts.

Fig.47_Facing with gauze and Tylose

Fig.48_Facing with gauze and Tylose

Fig.49_Facing with gauze and Tylose

Fig.50_Drilling angled hole

Fig.51_Preparing the pin: washer, gauze, screw, cotton and Polyfilla

Fig.52_Inserting the pin in position

Permanent stabilization of the decorative elements:

- Pinning with rawlplugs the detached areas of the flat fascia (Fig.53, Fig.54);
- Pinning with rawlplugs and washer the medallions (Fig.55 – Fig.58);
- Re-adhesion of two medallions detached during Phase 1.1 by (Fig.59 – Fig.64):
 - 1) measuring the medallion's center and the diameter on the wall and drill a hole in the center;
 - 2) reconstructing the missing part of the plaster on which the medallion leans with Polyfilla;
 - 3) reinforcing the back of the medallion by applying a protective layer (Paraloid B72 20% in acetone) and two layers of jute fibers (one vertical, one horizontal) soaked in Polyfilla;
 - 4) cutting into shape the washer to be placed at the center and lining the element by inserting the rawlplug + the screw and adding a layer of Polyfilla on the back of the medallion.

Fig.53_Assessing the detachment

Fig.54_Inserting the rawplug and screw

Fig.55_Drawing the washer's shape

Fig.56_Inserting the rawplug

Fig.57_Inserting the screw and washer

Fig.58_Medallion's pinning with rawplug and washer

Fig.59_Measuring the center and the diameter of the medallion

Fig.60_Reconstruction of the missing part by levelling with Polyfilla

Fig.61_Applying Paraloid B72 on the back of the medallion as protective layer

Fig.62_Reinforcing the medallion's back with two layers of jute and Polyfilla

Fig.63_Adding Polyfilla around the edges and at the center of the medallion's back

Fig.64_Re-adhesion of the medallion

6.3.1. Trials for Phase 2

Here are some sample tests that were carried out to show future phases of the treatment:

- Example 1: build a new anchoring system for arches' cornices (Fig.68 – Fig. 79);

As observed, these elements were casted and later applied on the surface without an anchoring system but stayed in place because they lean on the arches (Fig.65). Nevertheless, their intrinsic weakness puts them at risk of falling endangering people's safety since they are heavy and quite distant from the ground. Studying their stratigraphy from similar fragments found in the palace, we built an anchoring system to bypass the hollow space in their back to fix them permanently to the masonry (Fig.66, Fig.67).

We suggest following these steps:

- 1) Look at execution technique documentation to find elements joints;
- 2) Fix every module, drilling a hole in the middle of its length and at 1,5-2 cm of its width from the wall;
- 3) Check the position of the anchoring system and drill an angled hole (45 degree);
- 4) Measure PVC tube's length comparing it to the hole's depth and cut it (consider 3-4 cm extra);
- 5) Make an oblique cut at one end of the tube to facilitate its insertion within the masonry;
- 6) Mark the threaded galvanized steel rod's length comparing it to the hole's depth and cut it;
- 7) Insert the rod and the tube in the hole;
- 8) Inject Polyfilla in two phases: first injection to fill the area in the drilled masonry, second injection after pulling out the tube for 2 cm but keeping the rod in position (help yourself by pushing it inward with another rod). This operation helps anchoring better the rod to the Polyfilla injected in the masonry;
- 9) Cut the extra length of the tube;
- 10) Fill the voids around the tube with cotton soaked in Polyfilla, using a skewer to fix it in depth;
- 11) Fill the hole at surface level with Polyfilla.

Fig.65_Mapping of execution techniques East wall (1.5b): in green *casted elements*, in red *casted elements modelled by free hand (hybrid technique)*, in blue *elements modelled on the bench with running molds*

Fig.66_Comparison of execution technique with similar cornice

Fig.67_Drawing of the intervention

Fig.68_Definition of the drilling area

Fig.69_Pin position (45 degree angle)

Fig.70_Measuring lengths of the tube

Fig.71_Oblique cut of the tube

Fig.72_Marking rod's length on the tube

Fig.73_Cutting the rod

Fig.74_Inserting the rod and the tube

Fig.75_Rod and tube in position

Fig.76_Polyfilla injection

Fig.77_Cutting of tube's extra length

Fig.78_Filling of space around the tube with cotton soaked in Polyfilla

Fig.79_Filling with Polyfilla

- Example 2: Panel 4 treatment (Fig.80 – Fig.105);

The aim of this intervention is to consolidate all unstable elements and, when possible, reinforcing them from the back. We worked on panel 4 since its deformation was the worst among the others, deciding to remove the displaced element on the upper left corner and replacing it after the consolidation of the other elements. The intervention followed these steps:

Propping of the working area to stabilize decorative elements

Removal of upper left element

- 1) Cut the element around the edges;
- 2) Secure unstable/detached fragments with gauze and Paraloid B72 (20% in acetone);
- 3) Create an anchoring system (nail and twisted metal wire) to help the removal of the element from the wall by drilling in two positions (trying to hide the hole for minimal visual impact);
- 4) Transpose these two points to a foam panel (polystyrene) to be used as support during the removal;
- 5) Insert the anchors in the panel's drilled points and inside the correspondent holes in the foam panel,
- 6) Tie the anchors' metal wires around the wood stick that crosses the panel;
- 7) Remove the panel from the wall and set it on the working table.

Consolidation of the elements on site

- 1) Clean the area from debris and dust with puffer blower and brushes (remove any element that could hinder or compromise the planarity of the object);
- 2) Drill holes for punctual consolidation (injection of Polyfilla);
- 3) Reinforce the edges around the removed element by soaking jute fibers with Polyfilla and applying them partly on the support and partly on the back of the element with a spatula;
- 4) Inject Polyfilla around the edges, along the fibers;
- 5) Replace temporary pinning (screw, washer, Polyfilla and cotton) with rawlplug and screw.

Reinforcement of the removed element

- 1) Secure unstable elements with gauze and Paraloid B72 (20% in acetone);
- 2) Flip the element on the table (putting sand under it) to work on its back;
- 3) Engrave washer's shape in correspondence of the holes drilled during the removal of the element and the temporary consolidation;
- 4) Glue washers in place with Polyfilla;
- 5) Add a layer of Polyfilla on the surface and lay the reinforcing fibers on the surface (multiaxial fiber glass) by adding other Polyfilla;
- 6) Put a screw in the washer to re-open the holes that will be later used from the front.

Repositioning of reinforced element

- 1) Add Polyfilla in blocks on the back of the reinforced element;
- 2) Put element back in place checking its planarity and its matching with the rest of the decoration;
- 3) Insert screws in correspondence of the four fixed washers on the back.

Retouching and final aesthetic presentation:

- 1) Fill around the edges with Polyfilla;
- 2) Reconstruct the missing parts with Polyfilla;
- 3) Reintegration with watercolors.

Fig.80_Propping phase

Fig.81_Insertion of anchors

Fig.82_Fixing the anchors to foam panel

Fig.83_Removal of upper element

Fig.84_Panel after element removal

Fig.85_Drilling holes for consolidation

Fig.86_Elements' reinforcement

Fig.87_Injection of Polyfilla

Fig.88_Reinforcement of elements on site

Fig.89_Consolidation with Polyfilla injections

Fig.90_Securing unstable elements with gauze and Paraloid B72

Fig.91_Detail of gauze and adhesive

Fig.92_Flip of the element on sand

Fig.93_Engraving of washer's shape

Fig.94_Fixing the washers on the back

Fig.95_Application of first layer of Polyfilla

Fig.96_Application of the multiaxial fiberglass

Fig.97_Application of second layer of Polyfilla

Fig.98_Application of blocks of Polyfilla

Fig.99_Repositioning of the reinforced element

Fig.100_Replacement of temporary pinning with rawplugs and screws

Fig.101_Filling and reconstruction of missing parts

Fig.102_Panel before final reintegration

Fig.103_Panel during aesthetic presentation with watercolors

Fig. 104_Panel 4 before treatment (1.5b)

Fig. 105_Panel 4 after treatment (1.5b)

6.3.2. Future treatments (Phase 2)

To complete the conservation of the walls these further interventions will be needed:

Stabilization of the decorative elements:

- Consolidation of panels (see Example 2) and proceed according to the conditions for each panel;
- Replace temporary pinning on the panels with rawplugs and screws;
- Build anchoring system for arches' cornice (see Example 1).

Cleaning of the surfaces:

- Removal of dirt and products of alteration.

Reintegration of missing parts:

- Reconstruction of missing parts and casting of new elements according to existing decoration, filling of cracks and small losses.

Retouching and final aesthetic presentation:

- Retouching or reintegration of the painted layers;
- Reintegration of the gilding (gold).

6.4. Ceiling execution techniques

The structure of the coffered ceiling is the jack-arch slab system which is decorated by polychrome-painted arabesque tiles both casted and engraved by hand. The tiles are interlocked by a network of cornices modelled with running molds on the bench. The same hybrid technique was used for the *muqarnas*-style elements decorating the space between the ceiling and the cornice that runs along its perimeter. The perimeter ceiling is made according to the Baghdadi technique by building a wooden structure (joists and laths) fixed with metal brackets to the steel-I-beam of the coffered ceiling. On this structure a layer of gypsum-based plaster was later applied adding casted elements along the sides and decorations modelled by free-hand on site in the corners (Fig.106 – Fig.113). The perimeter cornice's structure was also observed from the inside taking advantage of missing parts along the decoration and by inserting a cellphone in between the laths (Fig.114 – Fig.116).

Fig.106_Observation of the perimeter cornice's structure

Fig.107_Analysis of the execution technique

Fig. 108_Detail of coffered ceiling

Fig. 109_Polychrome painted interlocked tiles

Fig. 110_Muqarnas-style element (joint between two modules)

Fig. 111_Perimeter cornice, casted elements

Fig. 112_Elements modelled by hand on site

Fig. 113_Detail, elements modelled by hand on site

Fig. 114_Bracket inside the masonry fixing the wooden structure (+ nails)

Fig. 115_Detail, bracket fixing the wooden structure to the masonry

Fig. 116_Structure of the perimeter cornice (view from the inside)

6.5. Ceiling condition assessment

The ceiling needs urgent structural intervention as a closer inspection of the surfaces assessed **severe damage of the Baghdadi structure of the perimeter cornice**. The blast caused the dislocation of the wooden structure from the rest of the ceiling causing other minor damages. In some areas, the joists along the sides of the room are completely separated from the wall as a result of the upward movement of the air coming inside the room during the blast. Other areas, on the contrary, were damaged by the opposite air's direction, after the suction effect, by the displacement of the brackets that levelled the joists with the steel-I beam of the jack-arch slab system of the coffered ceiling (Fig.117 – Fig. 120). The mechanical stress these decorations underwent caused cracks along the surfaces and losses of the original material but the gypsum on the laths and the wood is surprisingly in better condition compared to the structure. (Fig.120 – Fig.123). To have a better understanding of the damages suffered by the structure we suggest a further observation with endoscope. **The room is certainly not fit for use until taken care of with structural works.**

Fig.117_Crack along perimeter cornice

Fig.118_Detail, crack along the perimeter cornice

Fig.119_Muqarna's detachment from perimeter cornice

Fig.120_Total loss of plaster decoration

Fig.121_Upward detachment

Fig.122_Loss of decorated surface

Fig.123_Gypsum keys on laths

Fig. 124_Main hall ceiling (1.5b) before emergency measures treatment (ph. Kallas J.)

Fig. 125_Mapping of execution techniques main hall ceiling (1.5b): in green **casted elements**, in blue **elements modelled on the bench with running molds**, in red **casted elements modelled by free hand (hybrid technique)**, in orange **elements modelled on site by free hand**

Fig. 126_Mapping of conditions main hall ceiling (1.5b): in green **cracks**, in blue **detachments**, in orange **partial loss**, in red **total loss**

6.6. Ceiling Summer school treatments

Stabilization of the decorative elements:

Temporary

- Securing with gauze, screws and washers the unstable elements by stretching a gauze between two-tie points above and below the decoration (Fig.127 – Fig.131);
Muqarnas: for the upper areas by pinning with screws and washers the internal Baghdadi structure's joist, for the lower ones by pinning the base of the muqarnas. This operation was carried out only on the north-east corner of the cornice taking advantage of the missing parts in correspondence of the upper cornice modelled by running molds. This intervention allowed to observe the perimeter cornice internal sides and assess the severity of the structural detachment which inevitably led to the rethinking of the intervention's priorities. This problem was discussed on site with the owner and arch. Joe Kallas.
Cornice underneath muqarnas: by pinning a flat area in the muqarnas' background for the upper areas and a lower point on the decoration along the perimeter cornice width.
- Facing with gauze and adhesive (Tylose MH300 P 4% in water) the unstable elements (Fig.132– Fig.136);
- Edging repair of plaster missing parts.

Permanent

- Pinning with screws and washers the plaster decorations to the underlying wooden structure (Fig.132 - Fig. 136);
- Application of acrylic resin (Paraloid B72 20-25% in acetone) on wood by brush as protective layer for future application of gypsum (Fig.138 – Fig.139).

Fig.127_Securing with gauze, screw and washers the muqarnas

Fig.128_ Securing with gauze, screw and washers the muqarnas

Fig.129_Securing of the muqarnas element

Fig.130_Pinning with screw and washer in the joist

Fig.131_ Pinning with screw and washer in the joist

Fig. 132_Facing with gauze and adhesive the ceiling

Fig. 133_Facing of the ceiling

Fig. 134_Knock-test ceiling

Fig. 135_Gauze and adhesive application

Fig. 136_Facing detail

Fig. 137_Debris removal from laths

Fig. 138_Application of Paraloid on laths

Fig. 139_Edging repairs

Fig. 140_Securing with gauze, screw and washers

Fig. 141_Detail of the cut washer

Fig. 142_Securing of the unstable decoration

Fig. 143_Treatment on perimeter cornice

Fig. 144_Treatment on perimeter cornice (detail)

6.6.1. Trials for Phase 2

This is a sample test that was carried out to show future phases of the treatment:

- Example 1: pinning with screws the plaster decorations to the underlying wooden structure (Fig. 145 – Fig. 147).

Fig. 145_Measuring muqarnas' module

Fig. 146_Drilling in the middle of the module

Fig. 147_After pinning detail

Fig. 148_Mapping of interventions on the main hall ceiling (1.5b): in green facing with gauze and adhesive, in blue circles pinning with screw and washer, in blue crosses pinning with screws, in magenta Paraloid application on exposed wooden structure, in red securing with gauze, screw and washer.

6.6.2. Future treatments (Phase 2)

To complete the conservation of the ceiling these further interventions will be needed:

Stabilization of the Baghdadi structure: (VERY URGENT)

- Stabilize the wooden structure to the masonry:

Note: As discussed with arch. Kallas and the owner these could be the options:

- North/South walls: following the direction of the steel-I-beam (lengthwise), start by removing the muqarnas' upper cornice (modelled by running mold) and proceed by fixing/welding a new bracket between the masonry and the Baghdadi structure's joists (every 2 or 2,5 meters);
- East/West walls: following the direction of the steel-I-beam (crosswise and at regular 40-60cm intervals), start by removing the muqarnas' upper cornice or consider removing two muqarnas modules if necessary to reach the beam and fix/weld a new bracket between the masonry and the Baghdadi structure's joists (every 2 or 2,5 meters).

Stabilization of the decorative elements:

- Pinning of elements temporally secured with gauze and adhesive: insert 2-3 mm fiberglass bars at a 45 degree angle. Fiberglass can be also inserted by adding Polyfilla to create a further adhesive layer with the underlying structure;
- Pinning with screws all protruding elements considering their potential instability as described above (see example 1).

Cleaning of the surfaces:

- Removal of dirt and products of alteration;

Reintegration of missing parts:

- Reconstruction of missing parts with gypsum and casting of new elements according to existing decoration, filling of cracks and small losses.

Retouching and final aesthetic presentation:

- Hiding pinning interventions (see room 1.5c treatment, example 2);
- Retouching or reintegration of the painted layers;
- Reintegration of the gilding (purpurin).

7. SOUTH GALLERY (ROOM 1.5c)

Fig.149_ Gallery before the blast in 2019

Fig.150_ Gallery after the blast in 2021.

7.1. Execution techniques

The structure of the ceiling in Room 1.5c is a hybrid solution between the jack-arch slabs (central part) and the Baghdadi technique (coves). The decoration is mainly composed by elements modelled on the bench, both casted and modelled with running molds (Fig.151, Fig.152). The rosettes in the central area are all modelled by hand on site. Due to their white color, reconstructed parts done during previous interventions can be easily noticed on some areas of the cornices and on other spots (Fig.153).

Fig.151_Casted elements

Fig.152_Keyed surface underneath casted elements

Fig.153_Reintegrated element

7.2. Condition assessment

The plaster decorations of this room were badly conserved. The air movement of the blast caused a suction effect on the plasters that hardly returned to their original place, compromising the entire ceiling. The consequences of this mechanical stress, could be observed especially on the Baghdadi structure since three different types of detachment could be assessed (Fig.154, Fig.157):

- 1) detachment of the wooden ribs from the masonry;
- 2) detachment of the wooden lath from the wooden ribs;
- 3) detachment of the plaster from the wooden structure;

Often both the wooden elements and the plaster were also broken or overlapping because of the displacement they underwent. The pressure on the wooden structure, in some cases, caused the total loss of the plaster decoration.

Most of the casted elements, even the recently reintegrated, were detached due to the lack of anchoring system (Fig.158, Fig.159).

Fig. 154_Plaster decoration on Baghdadi

Fig. 155_Detail of the Baghdadi structure

Fig. 156_Detached wooden structure

Fig. 157_Broken rib

Fig. 158_Crack / Detached reintegration

Fig. 159_Total loss

Fig.160_Gallery (1.5c) before emergency measures treatment (ph. Kallas J.)

Fig.161_Mapping of execution techniques: gallery (1.5c): in green casted elements, in blue elements modelled on the bench with running molds, in red elements modelled on the bench by free hand, in orange elements modelled on site by free hand

Fig.162_Mapping of conditions: gallery (1.5c): in green cracks, in blue detachments, in orange partial loss, in red total loss, in magenta areas at risk of detachment

7.3. Summer school treatments

After the removal of the metallic nets, the first operations consisted in removing all unstable elements, tossing the debris (Fig.163) and keeping decorative parts that will be remounted during Phase 2. These decorations were photographed, labelled and put in a box to be stored in the owners' store (Fig.164, Fig.165).

Fig.163_Removal of debris

Fig.164_Removal of unstable elements

Fig.165_Inventory of collected parts

7.3.1. Phase 1.2

The securing of this ceiling started from the wooden structure of the coves, the most endangered part, proceeding from the top of the rib to the vault's impost in order to work systematically on the supporting base of the entire decoration. Some operations were carried out and later reviewed considering the overall intervention criteria: this led, for example, to the discarding of aesthetically invasive solutions in favor of permanent consolidations. The interventions were marked on site with red removable stickers to show the extent of the emergency measures carried out.

Permanent stabilization of the wooden structure (ribs and laths):

- Pinning with screws (9cm) the unstable ribs to the masonry structure;
- Repair broken ribs with wood and screws (Fig.166, Fig.167);
- Pinning with screws (9cm) the wooden laths to the ribs;
- Application of acrylic resin (Paraloid B72 20-25% in acetone) on wood by brush as protective layer for future application of gypsum (Fig.168).

Fig.166_Detail of a broken rib

Fig.167_New repair of broken rib

Fig.168_Acrylic resin application on wood

*Stabilization of the decorative elements:*Permanent

- Pinning with screws the casted elements (ribbon cornices) to the underlying rib, in case of planar areas, screws were inserted with a plate (Fig.169, Fig.170);
- Pinning with screws and washers the plaster decoration on the underlying rib (Fig.171, Fig.175);
- Securing with gauze and screws the vault's impost cornice: at first by stretching a gauze between two cross-tie points above and below the cornice. For the upper areas by pinning with screws and washers the plaster, for the lower ones by taking advantage of previous rawlplugs inserted in the wall to install the safety nets (Fig.172). Nevertheless, considering the aesthetic impact of this intervention, we decided to remove the gauzes and rather pin with screws the cornice itself to the underlying rib at regular intervals. (Fig.173, Fig.174);

Temporary

- Securing with gauze and nails unstable plaster decorations to the underlying wooden lath or rib (Fig.176, Fig.177);

Fig.169_Pinning a detached decoration

Fig.170_Pinning with screw and plate

Fig.171_Pinning with screw and washer

Fig.172_Stretching of the gauze

Fig.173_Securing with gauze and screws

Fig.174_Gauze removal from the cornice

Fig.175_Pinning plaster decoration on ribs

Fig.176_Securing with gauze and screws

Fig.177_Securing with gauze and screws

7.3.2. Trials for Phase 2

Here are some sample tests that were carried out to show future phases of the treatment:

- Example 1: build a new anchoring system for future reintegrations by fixing a torn steel wire to the wooden laths with screws (Fig.178, Fig.179);

Fig.178_Building of new anchoring system

Fig.179_Detail of the torn steel wire

- Example 2: Hide pinning intervention on plaster decorations by doing the following operations: remove screw and washer; engrave washer's shape in the plaster considering its thickness adding some extra space for the filling (do not overdo otherwise the lath will be exposed); put back screw and washer; fill with plaster (Fig.180 – Fig.183);

Fig.180_Pinning with screw and washer

Fig.181_Drawing of the shape to engrave

Fig.182_Engraving of the washer's shape in the plaster

Fig.183_Filling test (only on half part of the washer) to show the different phases of the operation

7.3.3. Future treatments (Phase 2)

To complete the conservation of the ceiling these further interventions will be needed:

Stabilization of the decorative elements:

- Pinning of elements temporarily secured with gauze and nails: insert 1 mm screws (on wooden structure) or 2-3 mm fiberglass bars (on masonry) at a 45 degree angle. Fiberglass can be also inserted by adding Polyfilla to create a further adhesive layer with the underlying structure;
- Pinning all protruding elements considering their potential instability (mapped on table as areas in risk of detachment) as described above.

Cleaning of the surfaces:

- Removal of dirt and products of alteration.

Reintegration of missing parts:

- Building a new anchoring system (see example 1);
- Reconstruction of missing parts with gypsum and casting of new elements according to existing decoration, filling of cracks and small losses.

Retouching and final aesthetic presentation:

- Hiding pinning interventions (see example 2);
- Retouching or reintegration of the painted layers;
- Reintegration of the gilding (purpurin).

Fig. 184_Gallery (1.5c) after emergency measures treatment: north side

Fig. 185_Gallery (1.5c) after emergency measures treatment

Fig. 186_Gallery (1.5c) after emergency measures treatment: east side

8. VESTIBULE (ROOM 1.9)

Fig.187_Vestibule after the blast in 2021

8.1. Execution techniques

The structure of the ceiling in the vestibule is the jack-arch slab system whereas the coves are made of gypsum boards. These boards are not connected to the flat part of the ceiling but rather are assembled in place by simply leaning them against a cornice (modelled on site with running mold) (Fig.188).

The plaster decoration stands out for its particularly fine workmanship: the main ornaments are all modelled by hand on site and are gilded with true gold (Fig.189). The other decorative elements are either casted (acanthus leaf cornice, egg and dart cornice, torus cornice, tiles) or modelled with running molds (both on the bench and on site) (Fig.190 – Fig.193).

Fig.188_Board leaning on the cornice

Fig.189_Elements made by hand on site

Fig.190_Casted tiles

Fig.191_Casted elements, cornices

Fig.192_Acanthus leaf molds' joint

Fig.193_Egg and dart molds' joint

8.2. Condition assessment

The suction effect of the blast, in this case, caused less damage because of the rigidity of the support. The most severe deterioration phenomena affecting the plaster decoration of the room, is the total loss of the gypsum boards of the coves (more or less extended based on the side, being the southern the worst). Due to the lack of a proper anchoring system and being hold in place only by a cornice modelled on site, these boards are very unstable elements that urge intervention (Fig.194 – Fig.195).

Partial losses of decorative elements were assessed along the impost cornices where casted modules were missing but also on the ceiling on some elements modelled by hand. This phenomenon was usually related to areas where cracks and/or detachments were found (Fig.196 – Fig.197).

Some elements that sounded hollow during the knocking test ended up detaching from the surface after a slight mechanical stress (Fig.198 – Fig.199).

The decorated tiles, being interlocked with each other, are at less risk of falling despite the lack of anchors and are not mapped as areas at risk of detachment.

Fig.194_ Total loss of the cove's gypsum boards

Fig.195_ Unstable gypsum board

Fig.196_ Plaster decoration on Bagdhadi

Fig.197_ Crack along the impost cornice

Fig.198_ Crack along the element modelled by hand on the ceiling

Fig.199_ Detachment of an element modelled by hand during the ceiling's assessment

Fig.200_Vestibule (1.9c) before emergency measures treatment (ph. Kallas J.)

Fig.201_Mapping of execution techniques: vestibule (1.9): in green *casted elements*, in blue *elements modelled on the bench with running molds*, in purple *elements modelled on site with running molds*, in orange *elements modelled on site by free hand*

Fig.202_Mapping of conditions: vestibule (1): in blue *detachments*, in orange *partial loss*, in red *total loss*

8.3. Summer school treatments

After the removal of the metallic net from the south wall, the first operations consisted in removing all the debris collected along the ceiling's impost.

8.3.1. Phase 1.2

Stabilization of the coves:

Temporary

- Facing with gauze and adhesive (Tylose MH300 P 4% in water) the unstable plaster decorations (Fig.203 – 204).

Permanent

- Chemical anchoring with bicomponent resin in order to fix the impost cornice to the masonry support according to the following steps: drill a hole in the cornice (on the planar area in the middle), clean the drilled hole, inject the resin, insert the screw (Fig.205 – Fig.209);

Fig. 203_Application of Tylose by brush on the gauze

Fig. 204_Facing with gauze and Tylose

Fig. 205_Chemical anchoring: drilling phase

Fig. 206_Chemical anchoring: removing dust and debris

Fig. 207_Resin injection

Fig. 208_Positioning the screw

Fig. 209_End of chemical anchoring

- Building of an external anchoring system (L-shaped) between the gypsum board and the exposed masonry according to the following steps: drill a hole in the support, position the steel bar measuring its length and bending it as needed, add a layer of gauze around the bar to protect the decorated surface from scratches, inject bicomponent resin, fix the steel bar in position (Fig.210 – Fig.212).

Fig.210_Building of L-shaped anchor: positioning of the metal bar.

Fig.211_Building of L-shaped anchor: checking the bar's shape.

Fig.212_Building of L-shaped anchor: adding a layer of gauze in between

Temporary stabilization of the decorative elements:

- Facing with gauze and adhesive (Tylose MH300 P 4% in water) the unstable plaster decorations;
- Edging repair of wall's plaster missing parts (Fig.213 – Fig.214).

Fig.213_Edging repairs on walls

Fig.214_End of edging repairs on walls

Permanent adhesion of detached fragments:

- Pinning of the element: choose an anchoring system (screw, nail, metal bar, fiber glass bar, etc.) and fix it to the fragment in a tilted position; drill a hole on the surface; add Polyfilla on the surfaces of both the fragment and the support; add Polyfilla and cotton in the hole while inserting the pin; keep the fragment in place by propping the surface. (Fig.215 – Fig.217).

Fig.215_End of edging repairs on walls

Fig.216_End of edging repairs on walls

Fig.217_End of edging repairs on walls

8.3.2. Future treatments (Phase 2)

To complete the conservation of the ceiling these further interventions will be needed:

Stabilization of the decorative elements:

- Fixing/Pinning of elements temporarily secured with gauze and adhesive: Considering the artistic value of these decoration, proceed as follow:
 - Fix elements of limited weight and thickness: use Paraloid B72 as a layer in between the fragment and the support, use an acrylic resin as adhesive. In case of partially detached elements, apply adhesive by injection;
 - Pin heavier/bigger elements: insert 2-3 mm fiberglass bars at a 45 degree angle. Fiberglass can be also inserted by adding Polyfilla to create a further adhesive layer with the underlying structure.
- Reinforcing of the internal part of the cove (back of gypsum board) with gypsum and fibers (hemp). Start by taking advantage of the missing parts and proceed with the reinforcement every 120cm, drilling holes if necessary.

Cleaning of the surfaces:

- Removal of dirt and products of alteration.

Reintegration of missing parts:

- Reconstruction of missing parts and casting of new elements according to existing decoration, filling of cracks and small losses.

Retouching and final aesthetic presentation:

- Retouching or reintegration of the painted layers;
- Reintegration of the gilding (gold).

9. CONCLUSIONS

Observations on the ceiling in the main hall showed a strong weakness of the perimeter ceiling, which is at high risk of falling. Its stability cannot be guaranteed because the condition of all mechanical constraints is unknown, therefore imminent intervention is suggested especially if the room is open to public. The indications of future phases of intervention were shared and discussed with arch. Kallas and are described in this report. **The owners are therefore invited to:**

- **intervene with the utmost urgency the structural consolidation of the perimeter cornice**
- **replace the protective nets in the central hall.**

The next phases of the treatment on the stucco decorations in these rooms can be concluded once the work on the architectural structure is completed. Future work should consider:

- the final consolidations
- the cleaning of the surfaces
- the reintegration of losses
- the retouching of missing parts and final aesthetic presentation

In agreement with the owners, we brought to SUPSI laboratories four decorative fragments to create molds to allow further replication during Giovanni Nicoli's course with SUPSI Bachelor students. Most of these fragments were found in boxes in the corridors with other materials with no indication of their original position (presumably collected during phase 1.1); only the ribbon cornice was removed during our intervention on the gallery's ceiling due to its instability. Regarding the glass tile fragment from the decoration of the first-floor central hall, our intention is to rebuild the original tiles' modules (6x6 and 3x6) and the glass with painted golden flowers.

Fig.218_Fragments brought to SUPSI laboratories

Fig.219_Ribbon cornice on site, gallery (1.5c)

Fig.220_Central hall first floor plaster decoration (2.5b)

Fig.221_Tiles detail, central hall first floor (2.5b)

10. FURTHER STEPS

One of the biggest challenges faced during this Summer school was the integration of students with different backgrounds. Their work was co-ordinated by the lecturers Giovanni Nicoli and Giulia Russo but required a lot of time and necessary breaks in which to recall theoretical concepts, repeat practical activities in order to realise successful treatments and discuss how to manage the gathering, exchange and archiving of information. Also, the movement and the mounting/dismantling of the two movable scaffoldings took a lot of time. In the future, the use of a permanent scaffold would increase the quantity of work that could be done.

Considering the possibility to organize in the future a second workshop or an intensive professional training course (tentative date January – February 2024), it would be advisable to integrate one or more professional plasterers into the team, who can ensure that the work set up during the workshop could be continued over time.

According to the needs of the site, different topics could be addressed:

- continue the emergency treatments (apply the methodological approach already established during the 2022 Summer school in rooms 1.1, 1.2 and 1.3 that are at high risk of losing the original decorations);
- continue the conservation-restoration interventions in the rooms secured during 2022 in order to finish the work and give a pilot project considering all the different steps needed to conclude the intervention (final consolidations, cleaning of the surfaces, reintegration of losses, retouching of missing parts and final aesthetic presentation);
- carry out a complete conservation-restoration intervention in room 1.3 (from the consolidation to integration and final presentation). In this case a scaffolding on the entire room will be needed.
- tackle new and more specific topics to train local professionals (e.g. grouting and adhesion of decorative plasters; connecting and repositioning of fragments).

In any case more funding will be needed to allow a third mission of SUPSI to take place.

Contacts with USEK and USJ could open the possibility to develop joined teaching activities (as USEK is doing with the University of Urbino in Italy), and in May 2023 a new call from the Leading House MENA will be opened (max request of fundings 40'000.00). Despite capacity building is not the aim of this cooperation partnership project, part of the activities could be directed to organize some field work.

In case it will be possible to fund travel and lodging expenses for students and lecturers from SUPSI (about 10-12 people), a two-week workshop could be organized in Spring 2024. In this case SUPSI will support the project, covering the costs of the lecturers' working hours and of all the materials.

In the meanwhile, to keep the attention on the palace alive, a half day conference on-line to discuss "The role of memory in the heritage conservation" is planned on April 3rd, 2023, organized by SUPSI (Giacinta Jean), RestArt Beirut (Patrick Michel) and UL (Yasmine Makaroun).

Dealing with buildings and surfaces profoundly damaged by a catastrophic event (explosion, flood, fire, earthquake ...) raises a great dilemma: reconstructing "as it was - where it was", erasing from memory the traces of the painful event, or integrate the memory into the reconstruction project, in a sensitive and critical way, considering the traumatic event as part of the history that over the centuries has made the building or surface what it is now.

The meeting intends to present different examples in which the debate on these two extremes is still alive and topical to understand how the discipline of conservation-restoration can help reflect on the complex historicity of works and on the presentation of a matter marked by events.

11. REFERENCES

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12. ANNEXES

- 12.1. **Materials inventory**
- 12.2. **CAD drawings**
- 12.3. **Material technical sheets**

12.1. Materials inventory

Palace Sursock Summer School, materials inventory

Materiale		Quantità	Scatola
Pacchetti spugne bianche	melamine sponges	24 (6 packs)	Box 1
Spugne spontex	Spontex sponges	3	Box 1
Spugne spontex compresse	Spontex sponges compressed	6	Box 1
Spugna verde abrasiva	Green abrasive sponge	1	Box 1
Spugne wishab	Wishab sponges	12	Box 1
Siringhe 20 ml	Syringe 20ml	48	Box 1
Siringhe 50 ml	Syringe 50ml	12	Box 1
Siringhe 60 ml	Syringe 60ml	2	Box 1
Siringe 1 ml	Syringe 1ml	20	Box 1
Aghi 16G	Needle 16G	15	Box 1
Aghi rosa	Pink needle	6	Box 1
Aghi grigi	Grey needle	3	Box 1
Rotolo cotone	Cotton roll	1 / 1.5	Box 1
Ciotoline medie silicone nero	Medium black mixing bowl	2	Box 1
Ciotola grande silicone verde	Big green mixing bowl	1	Box 1
Spazzolini	Toothbrush	4	Box 1
Soluzione fisiologica (fiale)	Saline solution	20x 2 ml doses	Box 1
Cucchiaini plastica	Plastic spoons	50	Box 1
Bastoncini bambù	Skewers	1 pacchetto (<100pcs)	Box 1
Maschere per la polvere	Dust masks	9	Box 1
Lame bisturi 10	Scalpel blade n10	50 pcs	Box 1
Lame bisturi 20	Scalpel blade n20	50 pcs	Box 1
Spatole in legno	Wooden spatulas	20	Box 1
Schizzetti (perette)	Puffer blowers	3	Box 1

Sursock Summer School, materials inventory

Materiale		Quantità	Scatola
Paraloid B44	Paraloid B44	1 kg	Box 2
Acril ME	Acril ME	1 l	Box 2
Scotch carta (spessori diversi)	Paper tape (different widths)	1/2	Box 2
Scotch da pacchi	Brown tape	2	Box 2
Scotch trasparente	Clear tape	1	Box 2
Scotch americano	Duct tape	2	Box 2
Bacchette fibre di vetro	Fiberglass rods	2	Box 2
Guanti nitrile S (100pcs)	Nitrile gloves size S	1	Box 2
Guanti nitrile M (100pcs)	Nitrile gloves size M	2 ½	Box 2
Guanti nitrile L (100pcs)	Nitrile gloves size L	1	Box 2
Rotolo juta	Jute fibers roll	1	Box 2
Carta giapponese	Japanese paper	10 fogli	Box 2
teli copri tutto 4x5m	Plastic covers 4x5m	2	Box 2
tende "zanzariera" 150x250	Mosquitos' curtain	2	Box 2
Pic solution Self fix Benda elastica	Elastic fixing bandages (Self fix Pic solution)	3	Box 2
Rotoli bende di garze – confezione 12	Stretch gauze bandage rolls	10 pz	Box 2
Tessuto quadriassiale in fibra di vetro	Multiaxial fiberglass fabric	4 mq	Box 2
Fascette	Cable ties	Circa 1 confezione	Box 2

Sursock Summer School, materials inventory

Materiale		Quantità	Scatola
Barattoli di plastica 100 ml	Plastic container 100 ml	1	Box 3
Barattoli di plastica 250 ml	Plastic container 250 ml	11	Box 3
Barattoli di plastica 500 ml	Plastic container 500 ml	1	Box 3
Barattoli di plastica 1000 ml	Plastic container 1000 ml	1	Box 3
Barattoli tappo rosso 100 ml circa	Plastic container with red lid (100 ml)	2	Box 3
Tylose MH 300 P	Tylose MH 300 P	180g (4 containers with red lid)	Box 3
Paraloid B72	Paraloid B72	500g	Box 3
Pennarello nero permanente	Black marker	1	Box 3
Pennarello verde punta grossa	Green marker	1	Box 3
Pennarello rosso punta grossa	Red marker	1	Box 3
Pennarello arancione punta grossa	Orange marker	1	Box 3
Pennarello viola punta grossa	Purple marker	1	Box 3
Pennarello blu punta grossa	Blue marker	1	Box 3
Rotolo pellicola trasparente	Plastic wrap roll	1	Box 3
Pennelli da vinci	Da Vinci brushes	4	Box 3
Pennelli Kremer	Kremer brushes	6	Box 3
Pennelli CTS n°30	CTS brush n°30	2	Box 3
Pennelli CTS n°40	CTS brush n°40	2	Box 3
Pennelli CTS n°50	CTS brush n°50	1	Box 3
Pennelli CTS n°60	CTS brush n°60	2	Box 3
Pennello viola piccolo	Small brush	1	Box 3
Rondelle in fibra di vetro rinforzate al 30% da 60mm	60mm reinforced 30%glass fiber washers	30 pz	Box 3
Punte avvitatore	Bit set for electric screwdriver	9	Box 3

Sursock Summer School, materials inventory

Materiale		Quantità	Scatola
Chiodo grezzo testa svasata 1,2x20	Flat head nail 1,2x20	pacco nuovo (40g)	Grey Box
Chiodo grezzo testa svasata 1,5x30	Flat head nail 1,5x30	1/3 pacco (20g)	Grey Box
Chiodo grezzo testa svasata 2,0x40	Flat head nail 2,0x40	½ pacco (100g)	Grey Box
Chiodo grezzo testa svasata 2,2x50	Flat head nail 2,2x50	¾ pacco (150g)	Grey Box
Chiodo grezzo testa svasata 1,7x10	Flat head nail 1,7x10	1 pacco (50g)	Grey Box
Cateteri misti	Canula	2 nuovi e 2 usati	Grey Box
Sacchi Polyfilla 5kg	Polyfilla 5kg	1	Grey Box
Barra filettata M10x50cm inox	Threaded galvanized steel rod M10x1m	8	Grey Box
Barra filettata M6x50cm inox	Threaded galvanized steel rod M6x50cm	9	Grey Box
Barra filettata M4x50cm inox	Threaded galvanized steel rod M4x50cm	11	Grey Box
Ancorante chimico Wurth WIT-PM 200	Bicomponent resin Wurth WIT-PM 200	1	Grey Box
Pistola manuale ancorante chimico	Wurth application gun	1	Grey Box
Miscelatori universali (pipette verdi)	Wurth applicator nozzles	15	Grey Box
Filo acciaio inox 1,00 mm 7m	Galvanized steel wire 1mm, 7m	6	Grey Box
Filo cotto bianco 2 fili da 1,00 mm	Galvanized iron wire 1mm	1	Grey Box
Viti legno tip snk 10x200 mm	Countersunk wood screw 10x200 mm	24 pz (nella scatola con le 10X260 mm)	Grey Box
Viti legno tip snk 10x260 mm	Countersunk wood screw 10x260 mm	10 pz	Grey Box
Viti svasate tx chrm 5x90/70 200 pz	Bugle-head torx 5x90/70 200 pz	1	Grey Box
Viti svasate tx chrm 6x140/70 100 pz	Bugle-head torx 6x140/70 100 pz	25pcs	Grey Box
Viti M6.0 X 100 mm	Screw M6.0 X 100 mm	20 pcs	Grey Box
Tubo cristallo extra 6x9 mm 2,5M	PVC tube 6x9 mm 2,5m	1	Grey Box
Tassello 5x30 c/viti 60 pz	Rawlplug 5x30 + nail screws	60 pcs	Grey Box
Tassello 6x80 c/viti	Rawlplug 6x80 + nail screws	16 pcs	Grey Box
Punta trapano SDS plus 5, 5 x 150 x 215	Hammer drill bit SDS plus 5, 5 x 150 x 215	2	Grey Box
Punta trapano SDS plus 5, 5 x 250 x 315	Hammer drill bit SDS plus 5, 5 x 250 x 315	1	Grey Box
Punta trapano SDS plus 4 x 100	Hammer drill bit SDS plus 4 x 100	3	Grey Box
Acetone	Acetone	2 L	Grey Box
Alcool	Ethanol	4 L	Grey Box
Rotolo fogli di plastica	Tracing papers	Different sizes	Grey Box
Documentazione grafica Summer School 2022	Graphic Documentation Summer School 2022	2 binders	Grey Box

12.2. Cad drawings

- Drawing 1: 1.5b_Main hall_EW_Panel 1 (TE, SC, IN)
- Drawing 2: 1.5b_Main hall_EW_Panel 2 (TE, SC, IN)
- Drawing 3: 1.5b_Main hall_EW_Panel 3 (TE, SC, IN)
- Drawing 4: 1.5b_Main hall_EW_Panel 4 (TE, SC, IN)
 - Drawing 5: 1.5b_Main hall_North and South elevations (TE, SC, IN)
- Drawing 6: 1.5b_Main hall_East and West elevations (TE, SC, IN)
 - Drawing 7: 1.5b_Main hall_ceiling (TE, SC, IN) + perimeter ceiling structure
- Drawing 8: 1.5c_South gallery ceiling (TE, SC, IN)
 - Drawing 9: 1.9_Vestibule ceiling (TE, SC, IN)

Drawing n° 1.1

TE

EXECUTION TECHNIQUES

LEGEND

- CASTED ELEMENTS
- CASTED ELEMENTS MODELLED BY FREE-HAND (HYBRID TECHNIQUE)
- ELEMENTS MODELLED BY RUNNING MOLDS ON THE BENCH
- ELEMENTS MODELLED BY RUNNING MOLDS ON SITE
- ELEMENTS MODELLED BY FREE-HAND ON SITE

1.5b_MAIN HALL - EAST WALL - PANEL 1

Scale: 1:20

TE

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Drawn by: Elise El Rassi, revised by Giulia Russo

Date: 08-07-2022

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Drawing n° 1.2

STATE OF CONSERVATION

SC

LEGEND

CRACK

PARTIAL LOSS

TOTAL LOSS

DETACHMENT

AREA AT RISK OF DETACHMENT

1.5b_MAIN HALL - EAST WALL - PANEL 1

Scale: 1:20

SC

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Drawing n° 1.3

IN

INTERVENTION

LEGEND

- SECURING WITH GAUZE AND NAILS/SCREW+WASHER
- SECURING WITH GAUZE AND ADHESIVE
- PINNING WITH RAWLPLUG AND WASHER
- PINNING WITH RAWLPLUG
- PINNING WITH SCREW, WASHER, POLYFILLA & COTTON
- CHEMICAL ANCHORING
- PINNING WITH SCREW, POLYFILLA & COTTON
- PINNING WITH SCREW AND WASHER
- PINNING WITH SCREW - 90 mm
- PINNING WITH SCREW - 150 mm
- APPLICATION OF ACRYLIC RESIN
- EDGING REPAIR
- TRIALS FOR PHASE 2
- POLYFILLA INJECTION
- RE-ADHESION OF PREVIOUSLY DETACHED ELEMENTS
- BUILDING NEW ANCHORING SYSTEM WITH PVC TUBE, STEEL ROD & POLYFILLA

1.5b_MAIN HALL - EAST WALL - PANEL 1

Scale: 1:20

IN

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Drawing n° 2.1

TE

EXECUTION TECHNIQUES

LEGEND

- CASTED ELEMENTS
- CASTED ELEMENTS MODELLED BY FREE-HAND (HYBRID TECHNIQUE)
- ELEMENTS MODELLED BY RUNNING MOLDS ON THE BENCH
- ELEMENTS MODELLED BY RUNNING MOLDS ON SITE
- ELEMENTS MODELLED BY FREE-HAND ON SITE

1.5b_MAIN HALL - WEST WALL - PANEL 2

Scale: 1:20

TE

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SC

Drawing n° 2.2

STATE OF CONSERVATION

1.5b_MAIN HALL - WEST WALL - PANEL 2

Scale: 1:20

LEGEND

CRACK

PARTIAL LOSS

TOTAL LOSS

DETACHMENT

AREA AT RISK OF DETACHMENT

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Drawing n° 2.3

IN

INTERVENTION

LEGEND

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1.5b_MAIN HALL - WEST WALL - PANEL 2

Scale: 1:20

IN

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Drawing n° 3.1

TE

EXECUTION TECHNIQUES

LEGEND

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- CASTED ELEMENTS MODELLED BY FREE-HAND (HYBRID TECHNIQUE)
- ELEMENTS MODELLED BY RUNNING MOLDS ON THE BENCH
- ELEMENTS MODELLED BY RUNNING MOLDS ON SITE
- ELEMENTS MODELLED BY FREE-HAND ON SITE

1.5b_MAIN HALL - WEST WALL - PANEL 3

Scale: 1:20

TE

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Drawing n° 3.2

STATE OF CONSERVATION

LEGEND

CRACK

PARTIAL LOSS

TOTAL LOSS

DETACHMENT

AREA AT RISK OF DETACHMENT

1.5b_MAIN HALL - WEST WALL - PANEL 3

Scale: 1:20

SC

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Drawing n° 3.3

IN

INTERVENTION

LEGEND

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1.5b_MAIN HALL - WEST WALL - PANEL 3

Scale: 1:20

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Drawing n° 4.1

TE

EXECUTION TECHNIQUES

LEGEND

□ CASTED ELEMENTS

□ CASTED ELEMENTS MODELLED BY FREE-HAND (HYBRID TECHNIQUE)

□ ELEMENTS MODELLED BY RUNNING MOLDS ON THE BENCH

□ ELEMENTS MODELLED BY RUNNING MOLDS ON SITE

□ ELEMENTS MODELLED BY FREE-HAND ON SITE

TE MAIN HALL - WEST WALL - PANEL 4

Scale: 1:20

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SC Drawing n° 4.2

STATE OF CONSERVATION

1.5b_MAIN HALL - WEST WALL - PANEL 4

Scale: 1:20

LEGEND

CRACK

PARTIAL LOSS

TOTAL LOSS

DETACHMENT

AREA AT RISK OF DETACHMENT

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Drawing n° 4.3

IN

INTERVENTION

LEGEND

- SECURING WITH GAUZE AND NAILS/SCREW+WASHER
- SECURING WITH GAUZE AND ADHESIVE
- PINNING WITH RAWLPLUG AND WASHER
- PINNING WITH RAWLPLUG
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1.5b_MAIN HALL - WEST WALL - PANEL 4

Scale: 1:20

IN

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1.5b_NORTH ELEVATION WALL

Scale: 1 / 50

TE

1.5b_SOUTH ELEVATION WALL

Scale: 1 / 50

TE

Drawing n° 5.1

EXECUTION TECHNIQUES

LEGEND

- CASTED ELEMENTS
- CASTED ELEMENTS MODELLED BY FREE-HAND (HYBRID TECHNIQUE)
- ELEMENTS MODELLED BY RUNNING MOLDS ON THE BENCH
- ELEMENTS MODELLED BY RUNNING MOLDS ON SITE
- ELEMENTS MODELLED BY FREE-HAND ON SITE

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CAMPUS

1.5b_NORTH ELEVATION WALL

Scale: 1 / 50

SC

1.5b_SOUTH ELEVATION WALL

Scale: 1 / 50

SC

Drawing n° 5.2

STATE OF CONSERVATION

SC

LEGEND

CRACK

PARTIAL LOSS

TOTAL LOSS

DETACHMENT

AREA AT RISK OF DETACHMENT

Project: SURSOCK PALACE BEIRUT - EMERGENCY MEASURES ON PLASTER DECORATIONS
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1.5b_NORTH ELEVATION WALL

Scale: 1 / 50

IN

1.5b_SOUTH ELEVATION WALL

Scale: 1 / 50

IN

Drawing n° 5.3

INTERVENTION

LEGEND

- SECURING WITH GAUZE AND NAILS/SCREW+WASHER
 - SECURING WITH GAUZE AND ADHESIVE
 - PINNING WITH RAWLPLUG AND WASHER
 - PINNING WITH RAWLPLUG
 - PINNING WITH SCREW, WASHER, POLYFILLA & COTTON
 - CHEMICAL ANCHORING
 - PINNING WITH SCREW, POLYFILLA & COTTON
 - PINNING WITH SCREW AND WASHER
 - PINNING WITH SCREW - 90 mm
 - PINNING WITH SCREW - 150 mm
 - APPLICATION OF ACRYLIC RESIN
 - EDGING REPAIR
- TRIALS FOR PHASE 2**
- POLYFILLA INJECTION
 - RE-ADHESION OF PREVIOUSLY DETACHED ELEMENTS
 - BUILDING NEW ANCHORING SYSTEM WITH PVC TUBE, STEEL ROD & POLYFILLA

Project: SURSOCK PALACE BEIRUT - EMERGENCY MEASURES ON PLASTER DECORATIONS
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Drawn by: Elise El Rassi, revised by Giulia Russo

Date: 08-07-2022

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Drawing n° 6.1

TE

EXECUTION TECHNIQUES

LEGEND

- CASTED ELEMENTS
- CASTED ELEMENTS MODELLED BY FREE-HAND (HYBRID TECHNIQUE)
- ELEMENTS MODELLED BY RUNNING MOLDS ON THE BENCH
- ELEMENTS MODELLED BY RUNNING MOLDS ON SITE
- ELEMENTS MODELLED BY FREE-HAND ON SITE

1.5b_EAST ELEVATION WALL

Scale: 1 / 50

TE

1.5b_WEST ELEVATION WALL

Scale: 1 / 50

TE

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SC Drawing n° 6.2

STATE OF CONSERVATION

LEGEND

- CRACK
- PARTIAL LOSS
- TOTAL LOSS
- DETACHMENT
- AREA AT RISK OF DETACHMENT

1.5b EAST ELEVATION WALL

Scale: 1 / 50

SC

1.5b WEST ELEVATION WALL

Scale: 1 / 50

SC

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USEK
UNIVERSITY OF SAINT-ESPRIT

Drawing n° 6.3

IN

INTERVENTION

LEGEND

- SECURING WITH GAUZE AND NAILS/SCREW+WASHER
 - SECURING WITH GAUZE AND ADHESIVE
 - PINNING WITH RAWLPLUG AND WASHER
 - PINNING WITH RAWLPLUG
 - PINNING WITH SCREW, WASHER, POLYFILLA & COTTON
 - CHEMICAL ANCHORING
 - PINNING WITH SCREW, POLYFILLA & COTTON
 - PINNING WITH SCREW AND WASHER
 - PINNING WITH SCREW - 90 mm
 - PINNING WITH SCREW - 150 mm
 - APPLICATION OF ACRYLIC RESIN
 - EDGING REPAIR
- TRIALS FOR PHASE 2
- POLYFILLA INJECTION
 - RE-ADHESION OF PREVIOUSLY DETACHED ELEMENTS
 - BUILDING NEW ANCHORING SYSTEM WITH PVC TUBE, STEEL ROD & POLYFILLA

1.5b_EAST ELEVATION WALL

Scale: 1 / 50

IN

1.5b_WEST ELEVATION WALL

Scale: 1 / 50

IN

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SWISS
CONSERVATION-RESTORATION
CAMPUS

Drawing n° 7.1

EXECUTION TECHNIQUES

TE

LEGEND

- CASTED ELEMENTS
- CASTED ELEMENTS MODELLED BY FREE-HAND (HYBRID TECHNIQUE)
- ELEMENTS MODELLED BY RUNNING MOLDS ON THE BENCH
- ELEMENTS MODELLED BY RUNNING MOLDS ON SITE
- ELEMENTS MODELLED BY FREE-HAND ON SITE

1.5b_MAIN HALL - CEILING

Scale: 1 / 50

TE

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Drawing n° 7.2

STATE OF CONSERVATION

SC

LEGEND

CRACK

PARTIAL LOSS

TOTAL LOSS

DETACHMENT

AREA AT RISK OF DETACHMENT

MAIN HALL - CEILING

Scale: 1 / 50

SC

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MAIN HALL - CEILING

Scale: 1 / 50

IN

Project: SURSOCK PALACE BEIRUT - EMERGENCY MEASURES ON PLASTER DECORATIONS

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OF SOUTHERN SWITZERLAND

MAIN HALL PERIMETER CEILING STRUCTURE

1 PERSPECTIVE VIEW

2

PERSPECTIVE VIEW

3 PERSPECTIVE VIEW

4

FRONT ELEVATION

Scale: 1 / 10

5

SIDE ELEVATION

Scale: 1 / 10

Project:

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Date:

08-07-2022

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<p>RestART Beirut</p> <p>دروسات بيروت</p> <p>SWISS CONSERVATION-RESTORATION CAMPUS</p>	

Drawing n° 8.1

TE

EXECUTION TECHNIQUES

LEGEND

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- ELEMENTS MODELLED BY FREE-HAND ON SITE

1.5c_SOUTH GALLERY - CEILING

Scale: 1 / 50

TE

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Drawing n° 8.2

STATE OF CONSERVATION

SC

LEGEND

1.5c_SOUTH GALLERY - CEILING

Scale: 1 / 50

SC

Project: SURSOCK PALACE BEIRUT - EMERGENCY MEASURES ON PLASTER DECORATIONS

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Drawing n° 8.3

IN

INTERVENTION

LEGEND

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1.5c_SOUTH GALLERY - CEILING

Scale: 1 / 50

IN

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Drawing n° 9.1

TE

EXECUTION TECHNIQUES

LEGEND

CASTED ELEMENTS

CASTED ELEMENTS MODELLED BY FREE-HAND (HYBRID TECHNIQUE)

ELEMENTS MODELLED BY RUNNING MOLDS ON THE BENCH

ELEMENTS MODELLED BY RUNNING MOLDS ON SITE

ELEMENTS MODELLED BY FREE-HAND ON SITE

1.9_VESTIBULE - CEILING

Scale: 1 / 50

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SC

Drawing n° 9.2

STATE OF CONSERVATION

LEGEND

CRACK

PARTIAL LOSS

TOTAL LOSS

DETACHMENT

AREA AT RISK OF DETACHMENT

1.9_VESTIBULE - CEILING

Scale: 1 / 50

SC

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1.9_VESTIBULE - CEILING

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12.3. Material technical sheet

67400 Paraloid™ B-72

Solid Grade Thermoplastic Acrylic Resin

Summary

Paraloid™ B-72 is an excellent general purpose acrylic resin, supplied as a 100 % solid grade or as a 15 % solution.

It can be applied in either clear or pigmented coatings by a variety of application methods and can be air-dried or baked. Paraloid™ B-72 has a very low reactivity with sensitive phosphorescent and luminescent pigments. The durability and non-yellowing characteristics also make it valuable for use with these pigments.

Paraloid™ B-72 is compatible with other film forming materials such as vinyls, cellulose, chlorinated rubbers, and silicones and can be used in combination with them to produce coatings with a wide variety of characteristics.

Paraloid™ B-72 is very resistant against water, alkalis, acids, oils and chemical fumes. The coverings are very elastic and adhere on many different surfaces, e.g. also on light metals.

Paraloid™ B-72 is unique in possessing a high tolerance for ethanol. The property allows its use in applications in which strong solvents cannot be tolerated. The alcohol dispersions may be cloudy or milky; however, clear, coherent films are formed.

Melting Point

Paraloid™ B-72 is an acrylic resin with a high molar mass, thus, it doesn't have a defined melting point. It starts to melt at 70 - 75°C; the flowing point is at 145 - 150°C. TG: 40°C

Physical Properties

(Not to be used as specifications)

Physical form	Pellets
Bulk density, 25°C, lb/gal	9.6
Solubility parameter	9.3
Transition temperature, T _g , °C	40
Ultimate hardness of clear films, KHN	10 to 11
Chemical composition	EMA Copolymer

Solubility of PARALOID™ -Acrylic Thermoplastic Resins

(Values given are Viscosity, cps, at 25°C of a 40% solids solution, except as noted)

Solvents	PARALOID™ Types				
	B-44 No. 67460	B-66 No. 67480	B-67 No. 67420	B-72 No. 67400	B-82 No. 67440
Alcohols					
2B Alcohol	- ^c	- ^c	- ^c	Dc	PS ^d
Isopropanol	-	-	2 800	-	-
n-Butanol	-	94 ^e	2 500	130 ^e	-
Isobutanol	-	5 600 ^{fg}	3 200	-	-
n-Amyl alcohol	-	-	3 200	-	-
Diacetone alcohol	10 000	6 200	2 300	3 500	3 000
Chlorinated Hydrocarbons					
Methylene chloride	2 700	850	520	960	1 200
Carbon tetrachloride	860 ^g	280 ^e	20 000	280 ^e	6 000 ^f
Ethylene dichloride	5 500	1 200	640	1 300	1 800
Trichloroethylene	12 000	7 200	2 100	4 800	3 400
Esters					
Ethyl acetate	1 800	940	240	500	610
n-Propyl acetate	1 800	570	180	550 ^g	580
n-Butyl acetate	2 600	875	250	700	630
Isobutyl acetate	3 100	960	240	660 ^g	700
Amyl acetate	5 600	1 110	320	850	980
1-Ethyl hexyl acetate	-	6 900	770	-	-
Ethers					
Dioxane	5 600	880	830	1 300	1 700

c. Code for used letters: - = Insoluble; D = Dispersed; PS = Partially soluble

d. Results when using pure 2B alcohol. Paraloid™ B-82 is soluble in different alcohol/water-mixtures.

e. Viscosity determined at 20 % solids.

f. Viscosity determined at 30 % solids.

g. Hazy solution.

C.T.S. S.R.L.

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Fax +39 081 7593118
cts.napoli@ctseurope.com

TYLOSE MH 300 P

COMPOSITION

Methylhydroxyethylcellulose

PHYSICAL AND CHEMICAL PROPERTIES

		HOECHST METHOD
Appearance	powder	
Solubility	soluble in cold water	
Ionicity	nonionic	
Active substance content	91.5% min.	8100
Moisture	7% max.	8130
NaCl content	1.5% max.	8150
Particle size <0.180 mm (through 80 mesh)	90% min.	8000
<0.100 mm (through 140 mesh)	25% min.	8000
Hoeppler Viscosity	270 - 350 mPas	8320
1.9% absolutely dry substance dissolved in water at 20°C		

STORAGE

If stored in closed bags in dry conditions, the product has a long shelf life.

PACKAGING

The product TYLOSE MH 300 P is supplied in 500 g and 2.5 kg pack sizes.

Tylose is a registered trademark.

Information contained in this data sheet is based on our state of knowledge and on laboratory testing at the above-specified date. The User should determine, by preliminary tests, the suitability of the product for his intended purpose, and should observe the laws and regulations regarding health and safety. C.T.S. S.r.l. guarantees the constant quality of the product but is not accountable for any damages caused by the incorrect use of a material. The product is intended for professional use only. In addition, the components and packaging can change at any time, without any obligation of prior notice.

STUCCO PER INTERNI IN POLVERE

DESTINAZIONE D'USO

Stucco in polvere per riempire fessure e buchi su mattoni ed intonaci e per rasature complete. Prodotto da gesso naturale e cellulose altamente collose, è facilmente miscelabile e non forma grumi. Non ritira, possiede una grande resistenza ed è a rapida essiccazione. Facilmente carteggiabile, dopo l'essiccazione permette l'inserimento di viti e chiodi.

CARATTERISTICHE

Aspetto del prodotto: stucco in polvere

Confezione: Scatola: 1 kg; Sacco: 5, 10 e 25 kg

Colore: bianco

Destinazione d'uso: solo per interni

Spessore minimo per strato: 0.5 mm

Spessore massimo per strato: 5 cm

Dimensione massima delle particelle: 100 µm

Tempo di lavorazione: 45 minuti

Tempo di essiccazione: 90 min

MESSA IN OPERA

Fondi: tutti i tipi di supporti murari in interno, asciutti, compatti e puliti. Utilizzabile su muri, soffitti, zoccolature e telai di porte e finestre. Ideale per supporti in intonaco, cemento, calcestruzzo, gesso, cartongesso, mattoni, pietre naturali...

Adatto inoltre per fissare cornici e rosoni in gesso, superfici in legno, pannelli per isolamento...

Operazioni preparatorie:

Eliminare eventuali parti in distacco dalle crepe e dalle zone da trattare. Spazzolare e spolverare accuratamente la superficie prima di applicare **Polyfilla Stucco per Interni in polvere**.

Le superfici molto porose e assorbenti devono essere preventivamente bagnate o trattate con un primer fissativo prima di applicare il prodotto.

Carteggiare le superfici molto lisce e lucide e verniciare preventivamente con un antiruggine teste di chiodi e parti metalliche per evitare il processo di ossidazione.

Preparazione dello stucco: Miscelare approssimativamente 2 parti di polvere con 1 parte di acqua fino ad ottenere la consistenza desiderata. Per ottenere un impasto omogeneo aggiungere sempre la polvere all'acqua e mescolare per circa un minuto.

Applicazione: Riempire i buchi, le crepe o le fessure da trattare. Rasare leggermente l'area trattata con una spatola umida. Lasciare essiccare. Se necessario carteggiare la stuccatura e quindi spolverare accuratamente prima di sovraverniciare.

Pulizia degli attrezzi: con acqua. Pulire gli attrezzi immediatamente dopo l'uso. Non gettare i residui nelle fognature.

Precauzioni/Osservazioni: non applicare a temperature inferiori a + 5° C o superiori a + 35° C (aria e supporto). Stoccare al riparo dal gelo, da temperature elevate e dall'umidità. Per una migliore conservazione del prodotto, richiudere accuratamente l'imballaggio subito dopo l'uso e conservare in luogo asciutto.

Tutte le informazioni tecniche qui contenute hanno carattere indicativo. Per informazioni più dettagliate si prega di consultare il nostro servizio di ASSISTENZA TECNICA.

Distribuito da:
AKZO NOBEL COATINGS S.p.A.
UFFICIO COMMERCIALE e
SEDE AMMINISTRATIVA:
28040 Dormelletto (No)
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SAFETY DATA SHEET

according to Regulation (EC) No. 1907/2006

ANCORANTE CHIMICO WIT-PM 200 -420ML (A)

Version	Revision Date:	SDS Number:	Date of last issue: 21.09.2021
11.1	05.05.2022	10676963-00008	Date of first issue: 14.10.2013

SECTION 1: Identification of the substance/mixture and of the company/undertaking

1.1 Product identifier

Trade name : ANCORANTE CHIMICO WIT-PM 200 -420ML (A)

Product code : 5918 240 420 (A)

Unique Formula Identifier (UFI) : HDY1-208X-600U-TK3D

1.2 Relevant identified uses of the substance or mixture and uses advised against

Use of the Sub-stance/Mixture : Adhesives
Professional use product

Recommended restrictions on use : Not applicable

1.3 Details of the supplier of the safety data sheet

Company : Würth S.r.l
Via Stazione
39044 EGNA (BZ)

Telephone : +39 0471 828 000

E-mail address of person responsible for the SDS : prodsafe@wuerth.com

1.4 Emergency telephone number

Centro Antiveleni di Milano 02 66101029 (CAV Ospedale Niguarda Ca' Granda - Milano)
Centro Antiveleni di Pavia 0382 24444 (CAV IRCCS Fondazione Maugeri - Pavia)
Centro Antiveleni di Bergamo 800 883300 (CAV Azienda Ospedaliera Papa Giovanni XXII)
Centro Antiveleni di Firenze 055 7947819 (CAV Ospedale Careggi - Firenze)
Centro Antiveleni di Roma 06 3054343 (CAV Policlinico Gemelli - Roma)
Centro Antiveleni di Roma 06 49978000 (CAV Policlinico Umberto I - Roma)

SECTION 2: Hazards identification

2.1 Classification of the substance or mixture

Classification (REGULATION (EC) No 1272/2008)

Skin sensitisation, Category 1 : H317: May cause an allergic skin reaction.

Long-term (chronic) aquatic hazard, Category 3 : H412: Harmful to aquatic life with long lasting effects.

SAFETY DATA SHEET

according to Regulation (EC) No. 1907/2006

ANCORANTE CHIMICO WIT-PM 200 -420ML (A)

Version	Revision Date:	SDS Number:	Date of last issue: 21.09.2021
11.1	05.05.2022	10676963-00008	Date of first issue: 14.10.2013

2.2 Label elements

Labelling (REGULATION (EC) No 1272/2008)

Hazard pictograms :

Signal word : Warning

Hazard statements : H317 May cause an allergic skin reaction.
H412 Harmful to aquatic life with long lasting effects.

Precautionary statements : **Prevention:**
P261 Avoid breathing dust/ fume/ gas/ mist/ vapours/ spray.
P273 Avoid release to the environment.
P280 Wear protective gloves.

Response:

P333 + P313 If skin irritation or rash occurs: Get medical advice/ attention.
P362 + P364 Take off contaminated clothing and wash it before reuse.

Disposal:

P501 Dispose of contents/ container to an approved waste disposal plant.

Hazardous components which must be listed on the label:

Tetramethylene dimethacrylate
Ehylene dimethacrylate
Methacrylic acid, monoester with propane-1,2-diol
2,2'-[(4-Methylphenyl)imino]bisethanol
Reaction mass of 2-[[2-(2-hydroxyethoxy)ethyl](4-methylphenyl)amino]ethanol and 2,2'-[(4-methylphenyl)imino]diethanol

2.3 Other hazards

This substance/mixture contains no components considered to be either persistent, bioaccumulative and toxic (PBT), or very persistent and very bioaccumulative (vPvB) at levels of 0.1% or higher.

Ecological information: The substance/mixture does not contain components considered to have endocrine disrupting properties according to REACH Article 57(f) or Commission Delegated regulation (EU) 2017/2100 or Commission Regulation (EU) 2018/605 at levels of 0.1% or higher.

Toxicological information: The substance/mixture does not contain components considered to have endocrine disrupting properties according to REACH Article 57(f) or Commission Delegated regulation (EU) 2017/2100 or Commission Regulation (EU) 2018/605 at levels of 0.1% or higher.

SAFETY DATA SHEET

according to Regulation (EC) No. 1907/2006

**ANCORANTE CHIMICO WIT-PM 200 -420ML
(A)**Version
11.1Revision Date:
05.05.2022SDS Number:
10676963-00008Date of last issue: 21.09.2021
Date of first issue: 14.10.2013**SECTION 3: Composition/information on ingredients****3.2 Mixtures****Components**

Chemical name	CAS-No. EC-No. Index-No. Registration number	Classification	Concentration (% w/w)
Tetramethylene dimethacrylate	2082-81-7 218-218-1 01-2119967415-30	Skin Sens. 1B; H317	>= 10 - < 20
Vinyltoluene	25013-15-4 246-562-2 01-2119622074-50	Flam. Liq. 3; H226 Acute Tox. 4; H332 Eye Irrit. 2; H319 STOT SE 3; H335 Asp. Tox. 1; H304 Aquatic Acute 1; H400 Aquatic Chronic 2; H411 M-Factor (Acute aquatic toxicity): 1	>= 2,5 - < 10
Ethylene dimethacrylate	97-90-5 202-617-2 607-114-00-5 01-2119965172-38	Skin Sens. 1; H317 STOT SE 3; H335 specific concentration limit STOT SE 3; H335 >= 10 %	>= 1 - < 10
Methacrylic acid, monoester with propane-1,2-diol	27813-02-1 248-666-3 01-2119490226-37	Eye Irrit. 2; H319 Skin Sens. 1; H317 specific concentration limit STOT SE 3; H335 >= 10 %	>= 1 - < 10
2,2'-(4-Methylphenyl)imino]bisethanol	3077-12-1 221-359-1	Acute Tox. 4; H302 Eye Dam. 1; H318 Skin Sens. 1; H317 Aquatic Chronic 3; H412 Acute toxicity estimate Acute oral toxicity: 959 mg/kg	>= 0,25 - < 1
Reaction mass of 2-[[2-(2-	Not Assigned	Acute Tox. 4; H302	>= 0,25 - < 1

SAFETY DATA SHEET

according to Regulation (EC) No. 1907/2006

ANCORANTE CHIMICO WIT-PM 200 -420ML

(A)

Version 11.1 Revision Date: 05.05.2022 SDS Number: 10676963-00008 Date of last issue: 21.09.2021
Date of first issue: 14.10.2013

hydroxyethoxy)ethyl](4-methylphenyl)amino}ethanol and 2,2'-[(4-methylphenyl)imino]diethanol	01-2119979579-10	Skin Irrit. 2; H315 Eye Dam. 1; H318 Skin Sens. 1; H317 Aquatic Chronic 3; H412 Acute toxicity estimate Acute oral toxicity: 619 mg/kg	
1,1'-(p-tolylimino)dipropan-2-ol	38668-48-3 254-075-1 01-2119980937-17	Acute Tox. 2; H300 Eye Irrit. 2; H319 Aquatic Chronic 3; H412	>= 0,1 - < 0,25
1,4-Naphthoquinone	130-15-4 204-977-6 01-2120760462-57	Acute Tox. 3; H301 Acute Tox. 1; H330 Skin Corr. 1C; H314 Eye Dam. 1; H318 Skin Sens. 1; H317 STOT SE 3; H335 Aquatic Acute 1; H400 Aquatic Chronic 1; H410 M-Factor (Acute aquatic toxicity): 10 M-Factor (Chronic aquatic toxicity): 10 Acute toxicity estimate Acute oral toxicity: 124 mg/kg Acute inhalation toxicity (dust/mist): 0,046 mg/l	>= 0,025 - < 0,1

For explanation of abbreviations see section 16.

SECTION 4: First aid measures

4.1 Description of first aid measures

- General advice : In the case of accident or if you feel unwell, seek medical advice immediately.
When symptoms persist or in all cases of doubt seek medical advice.
- Protection of first-aiders : First Aid responders should pay attention to self-protection,

SAFETY DATA SHEET

according to Regulation (EC) No. 1907/2006

ANCORANTE CHIMICO WIT-PM 200 -420ML (A)

Version	Revision Date:	SDS Number:	Date of last issue: 21.09.2021
11.1	05.05.2022	10676963-00008	Date of first issue: 14.10.2013

and use the recommended personal protective equipment when the potential for exposure exists (see section 8).

- | | | |
|-------------------------|---|---|
| If inhaled | : | If inhaled, remove to fresh air.
Get medical attention if symptoms occur. |
| In case of skin contact | : | In case of contact, immediately flush skin with soap and plenty of water.
Remove contaminated clothing and shoes.
Get medical attention.
Wash clothing before reuse.
Thoroughly clean shoes before reuse. |
| In case of eye contact | : | Flush eyes with water as a precaution.
Get medical attention if irritation develops and persists. |
| If swallowed | : | If swallowed, DO NOT induce vomiting.
Get medical attention if symptoms occur.
Rinse mouth thoroughly with water. |

4.2 Most important symptoms and effects, both acute and delayed

Risks : May cause an allergic skin reaction.

4.3 Indication of any immediate medical attention and special treatment needed

Treatment : Treat symptomatically and supportively.

SECTION 5: Firefighting measures

5.1 Extinguishing media

Suitable extinguishing media : Not applicable
Will not burn

Unsuitable extinguishing media : Not applicable
Will not burn

5.2 Special hazards arising from the substance or mixture

Specific hazards during fire-fighting : Exposure to combustion products may be a hazard to health.

Hazardous combustion products : Carbon oxides
Silicon oxides

5.3 Advice for firefighters

Special protective equipment for firefighters : In the event of fire, wear self-contained breathing apparatus.
Use personal protective equipment.

Specific extinguishing methods : Use extinguishing measures that are appropriate to local circumstances and the surrounding environment.

SAFETY DATA SHEET

according to Regulation (EC) No. 1907/2006

ANCORANTE CHIMICO WIT-PM 200 -420ML

(A)

Version	Revision Date:	SDS Number:	Date of last issue: 21.09.2021
11.1	05.05.2022	10676963-00008	Date of first issue: 14.10.2013

Use water spray to cool unopened containers.
Remove undamaged containers from fire area if it is safe to do so.
Evacuate area.

SECTION 6: Accidental release measures

6.1 Personal precautions, protective equipment and emergency procedures

Personal precautions : Use personal protective equipment.
Follow safe handling advice (see section 7) and personal protective equipment recommendations (see section 8).

6.2 Environmental precautions

Environmental precautions : Avoid release to the environment.
Prevent further leakage or spillage if safe to do so.
Retain and dispose of contaminated wash water.
Local authorities should be advised if significant spillages cannot be contained.

6.3 Methods and material for containment and cleaning up

Methods for cleaning up : Soak up with inert absorbent material.
For large spills, provide dyking or other appropriate containment to keep material from spreading. If dyked material can be pumped, store recovered material in appropriate container.
Clean up remaining materials from spill with suitable absorbent.
Local or national regulations may apply to releases and disposal of this material, as well as those materials and items employed in the cleanup of releases. You will need to determine which regulations are applicable.
Sections 13 and 15 of this SDS provide information regarding certain local or national requirements.

6.4 Reference to other sections

See sections: 7, 8, 11, 12 and 13.

SECTION 7: Handling and storage

7.1 Precautions for safe handling

Technical measures : See Engineering measures under EXPOSURE CONTROLS/PERSONAL PROTECTION section.

Local/Total ventilation : Use only with adequate ventilation.

Advice on safe handling : Do not get on skin or clothing.
Avoid breathing dust, fume, gas, mist, vapours or spray.
Do not swallow.
Avoid contact with eyes.

SAFETY DATA SHEET

according to Regulation (EC) No. 1907/2006

ANCORANTE CHIMICO WIT-PM 200 -420ML

(A)

Version 11.1 Revision Date: 05.05.2022 SDS Number: 10676963-00008 Date of last issue: 21.09.2021
Date of first issue: 14.10.2013

Handle in accordance with good industrial hygiene and safety practice, based on the results of the workplace exposure assessment

Take care to prevent spills, waste and minimize release to the environment.

Hygiene measures : If exposure to chemical is likely during typical use, provide eye flushing systems and safety showers close to the working place. When using do not eat, drink or smoke. Contaminated work clothing should not be allowed out of the workplace. Wash contaminated clothing before re-use.

7.2 Conditions for safe storage, including any incompatibilities

Requirements for storage areas and containers : Keep in properly labelled containers. Store in accordance with the particular national regulations.

Advice on common storage : No special restrictions on storage with other products.

Recommended storage temperature : 5 - 25 °C

7.3 Specific end use(s)

Specific use(s) : No data available

SECTION 8: Exposure controls/personal protection

8.1 Control parameters

Occupational Exposure Limits

Components	CAS-No.	Value type (Form of exposure)	Control parameters	Basis
Vinytoluene	25013-15-4	TWA	50 ppm	ACGIH
		STEL	100 ppm	ACGIH

Derived No Effect Level (DNEL) according to Regulation (EC) No. 1907/2006:

Substance name	End Use	Exposure routes	Potential health effects	Value
Tetramethylene dimethacrylate	Workers	Inhalation	Long-term systemic effects	14,5 mg/m ³
	Workers	Skin contact	Long-term systemic effects	4,2 mg/kg bw/day
	Consumers	Inhalation	Long-term systemic effects	4,3 mg/m ³
	Consumers	Skin contact	Long-term systemic effects	2,5 mg/kg bw/day
	Consumers	Ingestion	Long-term systemic effects	2,5 mg/kg bw/day
Methacrylic acid, mo-	Workers	Inhalation	Long-term systemic	14,7 mg/m ³

SAFETY DATA SHEET

according to Regulation (EC) No. 1907/2006

ANCORANTE CHIMICO WIT-PM 200 -420ML**(A)**Version
11.1Revision Date:
05.05.2022SDS Number:
10676963-00008Date of last issue: 21.09.2021
Date of first issue: 14.10.2013

noester with propane-1,2-diol			effects	
	Workers	Skin contact	Long-term systemic effects	4,2 mg/kg bw/day
	Consumers	Inhalation	Long-term systemic effects	8,8 mg/m ³
	Consumers	Skin contact	Long-term systemic effects	2,5 mg/kg bw/day
	Consumers	Ingestion	Long-term systemic effects	2,5 mg/kg bw/day
2,2'-[(4-Methylphenyl)imino]bisethanol	Workers	Inhalation	Long-term systemic effects	3,29 mg/m ³
	Workers	Skin contact	Long-term systemic effects	0,47 mg/kg bw/day
	Consumers	Inhalation	Long-term systemic effects	0,58 mg/m ³
	Consumers	Skin contact	Long-term systemic effects	0,17 mg/kg bw/day
	Consumers	Ingestion	Long-term systemic effects	0,16 mg/kg bw/day
1,4-Naphthoquinone	Workers	Inhalation	Long-term systemic effects	0,033 mg/m ³
Reaction mass of 2-[[2-(2-hydroxyethoxy)ethyl](4-methylphenyl)amino]ethanol and 2,2'-[(4-methylphenyl)imino]diethanol	Workers	Inhalation	Long-term systemic effects	9,8 mg/m ³
	Workers	Skin contact	Long-term systemic effects	1,4 mg/kg bw/day
	Consumers	Inhalation	Long-term systemic effects	2,9 mg/m ³
	Consumers	Skin contact	Long-term systemic effects	0,83 mg/kg bw/day
	Consumers	Ingestion	Long-term systemic effects	0,83 mg/kg bw/day
Ethylene dimethacrylate	Workers	Inhalation	Long-term systemic effects	2,45 mg/m ³
	Workers	Skin contact	Long-term systemic effects	1,3 mg/kg bw/day
	Consumers	Inhalation	Long-term systemic effects	1,45 mg/m ³
	Consumers	Skin contact	Long-term systemic effects	0,83 mg/kg bw/day
	Consumers	Ingestion	Long-term systemic effects	0,83 mg/kg bw/day
1,1'-(p-tolylimino)dipropan-2-ol	Workers	Inhalation	Long-term systemic effects	2 mg/m ³

SAFETY DATA SHEET

according to Regulation (EC) No. 1907/2006

ANCORANTE CHIMICO WIT-PM 200 -420ML**(A)**

Version 11.1 Revision Date: 05.05.2022 SDS Number: 10676963-00008 Date of last issue: 21.09.2021
 Date of first issue: 14.10.2013

	Workers	Skin contact	Long-term systemic effects	0,6 mg/kg bw/day
	Consumers	Inhalation	Long-term systemic effects	0,4 mg/m3
	Consumers	Skin contact	Long-term systemic effects	0,3 mg/kg bw/day
	Consumers	Ingestion	Long-term systemic effects	0,3 mg/kg bw/day

Predicted No Effect Concentration (PNEC) according to Regulation (EC) No. 1907/2006:

Substance name	Environmental Compartment	Value
Tetramethylene dimethacrylate	Fresh water	0,087 mg/l
	Marine water	0,009 mg/l
	Intermittent use/release	0,098 mg/l
	Sewage treatment plant	20 mg/l
	Fresh water sediment	3,12 mg/kg
	Marine sediment	0,312 mg/kg
	Soil	0,573 mg/kg
Methacrylic acid, monoester with propane-1,2-diol	Fresh water	0,904 mg/l
	Marine water	0,904 mg/l
	Intermittent use/release	0,972 mg/l
	Sewage treatment plant	10 mg/l
	Fresh water sediment	6,28 mg/kg
	Marine sediment	6,28 mg/kg
	Soil	0,727 mg/kg
2,2'-[(4-Methylphenyl)imino]bisethanol	Fresh water	0,026 mg/l
	Freshwater - intermittent	0,26 mg/l
	Marine water	0,003 mg/l
	Marine water - intermittent	0,026 mg/l
	Sewage treatment plant	10 mg/l
	Fresh water sediment	0,121 mg/kg dry weight (d.w.)
	Marine sediment	0,012 mg/kg dry weight (d.w.)
1,4-Naphthoquinone	Soil	0,009 mg/kg dry weight (d.w.)
	Fresh water	0,0261 µg/l
	Freshwater - intermittent	0,261 µg/l
	Marine water	0,00261 µg/l
	Marine water - intermittent	0,0261 µg/l
	Sewage treatment plant	0,172 mg/l
	Fresh water sediment	0,000321 mg/kg dry weight (d.w.)
Reaction mass of 2-[[2-(2-hydroxyethoxy)ethyl](4-	Marine sediment	0,000032 mg/kg dry weight (d.w.)
	Soil	0,000049 mg/kg dry weight (d.w.)
	Fresh water	0,048 mg/l

SAFETY DATA SHEET

according to Regulation (EC) No. 1907/2006

ANCORANTE CHIMICO WIT-PM 200 -420ML (A)

Version 11.1 Revision Date: 05.05.2022 SDS Number: 10676963-00008 Date of last issue: 21.09.2021
Date of first issue: 14.10.2013

methylphenyl)amino}ethanol and 2,2'-[(4-methylphenyl)imino]diethanol		
	Freshwater - intermittent	0,48 mg/l
	Marine water	0,005 mg/l
	Sewage treatment plant	10 mg/l
	Fresh water sediment	1,2 mg/kg dry weight (d.w.)
	Marine sediment	0,12 mg/kg dry weight (d.w.)
	Soil	0,21 mg/kg dry weight (d.w.)
Ehylene dimethacrylate	Fresh water	0,139 mg/l
	Marine water	0,0139 mg/l
	Intermittent use/release	0,15 mg/l
	Sewage treatment plant	57 mg/l
	Fresh water sediment	1,6 mg/kg
	Marine sediment	0,16 mg/kg
	Soil	0,239 mg/kg
1,1'-(p-tolylimino)dipropan-2-ol	Fresh water	0,017 mg/l
	Marine water	0,0017 mg/l
	Intermittent use/release	0,17 mg/l
	Sewage treatment plant	199,5 mg/l
	Fresh water sediment	0,0782 mg/kg
	Marine sediment	0,00782 mg/kg
	Soil	0,005 mg/kg

8.2 Exposure controls

Engineering measures

Ensure adequate ventilation, especially in confined areas.
Minimize workplace exposure concentrations.

Personal protective equipment

Eye protection : Wear the following personal protective equipment:
Safety glasses
Equipment should conform to UNI EN 166

Hand protection

Material : Nitrile rubber
Break through time : > 480 min
Glove thickness : 0,5 mm
Directive : Equipment should conform to UNI EN 374

Remarks : Choose gloves to protect hands against chemicals depending on the concentration and quantity of the hazardous substance and specific to place of work. For special applications, we recommend clarifying the resistance to chemicals of the aforementioned protective gloves with the glove manufacturer. Wash hands before breaks and at the end of workday.

Skin and body protection : Select appropriate protective clothing based on chemical

SAFETY DATA SHEET

according to Regulation (EC) No. 1907/2006

ANCORANTE CHIMICO WIT-PM 200 -420ML (A)

Version	Revision Date:	SDS Number:	Date of last issue: 21.09.2021
11.1	05.05.2022	10676963-00008	Date of first issue: 14.10.2013

resistance data and an assessment of the local exposure potential.
Skin contact must be avoided by using impervious protective clothing (gloves, aprons, boots, etc).

Respiratory protection : If adequate local exhaust ventilation is not available or exposure assessment demonstrates exposures outside the recommended guidelines, use respiratory protection.
Equipment should conform to UNI EN 14387

Filter type : Combined particulates and organic vapour type (A-P)

SECTION 9: Physical and chemical properties

9.1 Information on basic physical and chemical properties

Physical state	: paste
Colour	: beige
Odour	: characteristic
Odour Threshold	: No data available
Melting point/freezing point	: No data available
Initial boiling point and boiling range	: No data available
Flammability (solid, gas)	: Not classified as a flammability hazard
Upper explosion limit / Upper flammability limit	: No data available
Lower explosion limit / Lower flammability limit	: No data available
Flash point	: Not applicable
Auto-ignition temperature	: No data available
Decomposition temperature	: No data available
pH	: substance/mixture is non-soluble (in water)
Viscosity	
Viscosity, kinematic	: Not applicable
Solubility(ies)	
Water solubility	: insoluble

SAFETY DATA SHEET

according to Regulation (EC) No. 1907/2006

ANCORANTE CHIMICO WIT-PM 200 -420ML (A)

Version	Revision Date:	SDS Number:	Date of last issue: 21.09.2021
11.1	05.05.2022	10676963-00008	Date of first issue: 14.10.2013

Partition coefficient: n-octanol/water	:	Not applicable
Vapour pressure	:	Not applicable
Density	:	1,72 g/cm ³ (20 °C)
Relative vapour density	:	Not applicable
Particle characteristics Particle size	:	No data available

9.2 Other information

Explosives	:	Not explosive
Oxidizing properties	:	The substance or mixture is not classified as oxidizing.
Evaporation rate	:	Not applicable

SECTION 10: Stability and reactivity

10.1 Reactivity

Not classified as a reactivity hazard.

10.2 Chemical stability

Stable under normal conditions.

10.3 Possibility of hazardous reactions

Hazardous reactions	:	None known.
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10.4 Conditions to avoid

Conditions to avoid	:	None known.
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10.5 Incompatible materials

Materials to avoid	:	None.
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10.6 Hazardous decomposition products

No hazardous decomposition products are known.

SECTION 11: Toxicological information

11.1 Information on hazard classes as defined in Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008

Information on likely routes of exposure	:	Skin contact Ingestion Eye contact
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SAFETY DATA SHEET

according to Regulation (EC) No. 1907/2006

ANCORANTE CHIMICO WIT-PM 200 -420ML (A)

Version 11.1 Revision Date: 05.05.2022 SDS Number: 10676963-00008 Date of last issue: 21.09.2021
Date of first issue: 14.10.2013

Acute toxicity

Not classified based on available information.

Product:

Acute oral toxicity : Acute toxicity estimate: > 2.000 mg/kg
Method: Calculation method

Acute inhalation toxicity : Acute toxicity estimate: > 20 mg/l
Exposure time: 4 h
Test atmosphere: vapour
Method: Calculation method

Components:

Tetramethylene dimethacrylate:

Acute oral toxicity : LD50 (Rat): 10.066 mg/kg

Acute dermal toxicity : LD50 (Rabbit): > 2.000 mg/kg
Remarks: Based on data from similar materials

Vinyltoluene:

Acute oral toxicity : LD50 (Rat): 4.000 mg/kg

Acute inhalation toxicity : LC50 (Rat): > 14 mg/l
Exposure time: 4 h
Test atmosphere: vapour
Remarks: Based on data from similar materials

Acute dermal toxicity : LD50 (Rabbit): > 4.585 mg/kg
Remarks: Based on data from similar materials

Ethylene dimethacrylate:

Acute oral toxicity : LD50 (Rat): 8.300 mg/kg

Acute dermal toxicity : LD50 (Rat): > 2.000 mg/kg
Method: OECD Test Guideline 402
Assessment: The substance or mixture has no acute dermal toxicity

Methacrylic acid, monoester with propane-1,2-diol:

Acute oral toxicity : LD50 (Rat): > 2.000 mg/kg
Method: OECD Test Guideline 401
Assessment: The substance or mixture has no acute oral toxicity

Acute dermal toxicity : LD50 (Rabbit): > 5.000 mg/kg

2,2'-[(4-Methylphenyl)imino]bisethanol:

Acute oral toxicity : LD50 (Rat): 959 mg/kg

SAFETY DATA SHEET

according to Regulation (EC) No. 1907/2006

ANCORANTE CHIMICO WIT-PM 200 -420ML (A)

Version 11.1 Revision Date: 05.05.2022 SDS Number: 10676963-00008 Date of last issue: 21.09.2021
Date of first issue: 14.10.2013

Acute toxicity estimate: 959 mg/kg
Method: Calculation method

Acute dermal toxicity : LD50 (Rat): > 2.000 mg/kg
Method: OECD Test Guideline 402
Remarks: Based on data from similar materials

Reaction mass of 2-[[2-(2-hydroxyethoxy)ethyl](4-methylphenyl)amino]ethanol and 2,2'-[[4-methylphenyl]imino]diethanol:

Acute oral toxicity : LD50 (Rat, male): 619 mg/kg
Method: OECD Test Guideline 401

Acute toxicity estimate: 619 mg/kg
Method: Calculation method

Acute dermal toxicity : LD50 (Rat): > 2.000 mg/kg
Method: OECD Test Guideline 402

1,1'-(p-tolylimino)dipropan-2-ol:

Acute oral toxicity : LD50 (Rat): > 25 - 200 mg/kg
Method: OECD Test Guideline 423

Acute dermal toxicity : LD50 (Rat): > 2.000 mg/kg
Method: OECD Test Guideline 402
Assessment: The substance or mixture has no acute dermal toxicity

1,4-Naphthoquinone:

Acute oral toxicity : LD50 (Rat): 124 mg/kg

Acute toxicity estimate: 124 mg/kg
Method: Calculation method

Acute inhalation toxicity : LC50 (Rat): 0,046 mg/l
Exposure time: 4 h
Test atmosphere: dust/mist
Method: OECD Test Guideline 403

Acute toxicity estimate: 0,046 mg/l
Test atmosphere: dust/mist
Method: Calculation method

Skin corrosion/irritation

Not classified based on available information.

Components:

Tetramethylene dimethacrylate:

Species : Rabbit

SAFETY DATA SHEET

according to Regulation (EC) No. 1907/2006

ANCORANTE CHIMICO WIT-PM 200 -420ML (A)

Version	Revision Date:	SDS Number:	Date of last issue: 21.09.2021
11.1	05.05.2022	10676963-00008	Date of first issue: 14.10.2013

Result : No skin irritation

Ethylene dimethacrylate:

Species : Rabbit
Result : No skin irritation

Methacrylic acid, monoester with propane-1,2-diol:

Species : Rabbit
Result : No skin irritation

2,2'-[(4-Methylphenyl)imino]bisethanol:

Species : Rabbit
Result : No skin irritation

Reaction mass of 2-[[2-(2-hydroxyethoxy)ethyl](4-methylphenyl)amino]ethanol and 2,2'-[(4-methylphenyl)imino]diethanol:

Species : reconstructed human epidermis (RhE)
Method : OECD Test Guideline 431

Species : reconstructed human epidermis (RhE)
Method : OECD Test Guideline 439

Result : Skin irritation

1,1'-(p-tolylimino)dipropan-2-ol:

Species : Rabbit
Method : OECD Test Guideline 404
Result : No skin irritation

1,4-Naphthoquinone:

Species : Rabbit
Method : OECD Test Guideline 404
Result : Corrosive after 1 to 4 hours of exposure

Serious eye damage/eye irritation

Not classified based on available information.

Components:

Tetramethylene dimethacrylate:

Species : Rabbit
Result : No eye irritation

Vinyltoluene:

Result : Irritation to eyes, reversing within 21 days

SAFETY DATA SHEET

according to Regulation (EC) No. 1907/2006

ANCORANTE CHIMICO WIT-PM 200 -420ML (A)

Version	Revision Date:	SDS Number:	Date of last issue: 21.09.2021
11.1	05.05.2022	10676963-00008	Date of first issue: 14.10.2013

Ethylene dimethacrylate:

Species : Rabbit
Result : No eye irritation

Methacrylic acid, monoester with propane-1,2-diol:

Species : Rabbit
Result : Irritation to eyes, reversing within 21 days

2,2'-[(4-Methylphenyl)imino]bisethanol:

Species : Rabbit
Result : Irreversible effects on the eye

Reaction mass of 2-[[2-(2-hydroxyethoxy)ethyl](4-methylphenyl)amino]ethanol and 2,2'-[(4-methylphenyl)imino]diethanol:

Species : Rabbit
Method : OECD Test Guideline 405
Result : Irreversible effects on the eye

1,1'-(p-tolylimino)dipropan-2-ol:

Species : Rabbit
Method : OECD Test Guideline 405
Result : Irritation to eyes, reversing within 7 days

1,4-Naphthoquinone:

Result : Irreversible effects on the eye
Remarks : Based on skin corrosivity.

Respiratory or skin sensitisation

Skin sensitisation

May cause an allergic skin reaction.

Respiratory sensitisation

Not classified based on available information.

Components:

Tetramethylene dimethacrylate:

Test Type : Local lymph node assay (LLNA)
Exposure routes : Skin contact
Species : Mouse
Method : OECD Test Guideline 429
Result : positive

Assessment : Probability or evidence of low to moderate skin sensitisation rate in humans

Vinyltoluene:

SAFETY DATA SHEET

according to Regulation (EC) No. 1907/2006

ANCORANTE CHIMICO WIT-PM 200 -420ML (A)

Version 11.1 Revision Date: 05.05.2022 SDS Number: 10676963-00008 Date of last issue: 21.09.2021
Date of first issue: 14.10.2013

Test Type : Maximisation Test
Exposure routes : Skin contact
Species : Guinea pig
Method : OECD Test Guideline 406
Result : negative

Ethylene dimethacrylate:

Test Type : Local lymph node assay (LLNA)
Exposure routes : Skin contact
Species : Mouse
Method : OECD Test Guideline 429
Result : positive

Assessment : Probability or evidence of skin sensitisation in humans

Methacrylic acid, monoester with propane-1,2-diol:

Species : Guinea pig
Result : positive

Assessment : Probability or evidence of skin sensitisation in humans

2,2'-[(4-Methylphenyl)imino]bisethanol:

Test Type : Local lymph node assay (LLNA)
Exposure routes : Skin contact
Species : Mouse
Method : OECD Test Guideline 429
Result : positive
Remarks : Based on data from similar materials

Assessment : Probability or evidence of skin sensitisation in humans

Reaction mass of 2-[[2-(2-hydroxyethoxy)ethyl](4-methylphenyl)amino]ethanol and 2,2'-[(4-methylphenyl)imino]diethanol:

Test Type : Local lymph node assay (LLNA)
Exposure routes : Skin contact
Species : Mouse
Method : OECD Test Guideline 429
Result : positive

Assessment : Probability or evidence of skin sensitisation in humans

1,1'-(p-tolylimino)dipropan-2-ol:

Test Type : Maximisation Test
Exposure routes : Skin contact
Species : Guinea pig
Method : OECD Test Guideline 406
Result : negative

SAFETY DATA SHEET

according to Regulation (EC) No. 1907/2006

ANCORANTE CHIMICO WIT-PM 200 -420ML (A)

Version	Revision Date:	SDS Number:	Date of last issue: 21.09.2021
11.1	05.05.2022	10676963-00008	Date of first issue: 14.10.2013

1,4-Naphthoquinone:

Exposure routes : Skin contact
Species : Guinea pig
Result : positive

Assessment : Probability or evidence of skin sensitisation in humans

Germ cell mutagenicity

Not classified based on available information.

Components:

Tetramethylene dimethacrylate:

Genotoxicity in vitro : Test Type: Bacterial reverse mutation assay (AMES)
Method: OECD Test Guideline 471
Result: negative

Test Type: Chromosome aberration test in vitro
Method: OECD Test Guideline 473
Result: negative

Test Type: In vitro mammalian cell gene mutation test
Method: OECD Test Guideline 476
Result: negative

Genotoxicity in vivo : Test Type: Mammalian erythrocyte micronucleus test (in vivo
cytogenetic assay)
Species: Mouse
Application Route: Ingestion
Method: OECD Test Guideline 474
Result: negative

Vinyltoluene:

Genotoxicity in vitro : Test Type: Bacterial reverse mutation assay (AMES)
Method: OECD Test Guideline 471
Result: negative

Test Type: In vitro mammalian cell gene mutation test
Result: positive

Test Type: Chromosome aberration test in vitro
Result: negative

Genotoxicity in vivo : Test Type: Mutagenicity (in vivo mammalian bone-marrow
cytogenetic test, chromosomal analysis)
Species: Rat
Application Route: Ingestion
Result: negative
Remarks: Based on data from similar materials

Test Type: Rodent dominant lethal test (germ cell) (in vivo)

SAFETY DATA SHEET

according to Regulation (EC) No. 1907/2006

ANCORANTE CHIMICO WIT-PM 200 -420ML

(A)

Version	Revision Date:	SDS Number:	Date of last issue: 21.09.2021
11.1	05.05.2022	10676963-00008	Date of first issue: 14.10.2013

Species: Rat
Application Route: Ingestion
Result: negative

Ethylene dimethacrylate:

Genotoxicity in vitro : Test Type: Bacterial reverse mutation assay (AMES)
Result: negative

Test Type: Chromosome aberration test in vitro
Method: OECD Test Guideline 473
Result: positive

Test Type: In vitro mammalian cell gene mutation test
Method: OECD Test Guideline 476
Result: negative

Genotoxicity in vivo : Test Type: Mammalian erythrocyte micronucleus test (in vivo cytogenetic assay)
Species: Mouse
Application Route: Ingestion
Method: OECD Test Guideline 474
Result: negative

Methacrylic acid, monoester with propane-1,2-diol:

Genotoxicity in vitro : Test Type: Bacterial reverse mutation assay (AMES)
Method: OECD Test Guideline 471
Result: negative

Genotoxicity in vivo : Test Type: Mammalian erythrocyte micronucleus test (in vivo cytogenetic assay)
Species: Rat
Application Route: Ingestion
Method: OECD Test Guideline 474
Result: negative

2,2'-[(4-Methylphenyl)imino]bisethanol:

Genotoxicity in vitro : Test Type: Bacterial reverse mutation assay (AMES)
Result: negative

Test Type: In vitro mammalian cell gene mutation test
Method: OECD Test Guideline 476
Result: positive
Remarks: Based on data from similar materials

Test Type: Chromosome aberration test in vitro
Method: OECD Test Guideline 473
Result: negative
Remarks: Based on data from similar materials

Genotoxicity in vivo : Test Type: In vivo mammalian alkaline comet assay

SAFETY DATA SHEET

according to Regulation (EC) No. 1907/2006

ANCORANTE CHIMICO WIT-PM 200 -420ML

(A)

Version	Revision Date:	SDS Number:	Date of last issue: 21.09.2021
11.1	05.05.2022	10676963-00008	Date of first issue: 14.10.2013

Species: Rat
Application Route: Ingestion
Method: OECD Test Guideline 489
Result: negative
Remarks: Based on data from similar materials

Reaction mass of 2-[[2-(2-hydroxyethoxy)ethyl](4-methylphenyl)amino]ethanol and 2,2'-[[4-methylphenyl]imino]diethanol:

Genotoxicity in vitro : Test Type: Bacterial reverse mutation assay (AMES)
Method: OECD Test Guideline 471
Result: negative

Test Type: In vitro mammalian cell gene mutation test
Method: OECD Test Guideline 476
Result: positive

Test Type: Chromosome aberration test in vitro
Method: OECD Test Guideline 473
Result: negative

Genotoxicity in vivo : Test Type: In vivo mammalian alkaline comet assay
Species: Rat
Application Route: Ingestion
Method: OECD Test Guideline 489
Result: negative

1,1'-(p-tolylimino)dipropan-2-ol:

Genotoxicity in vitro : Test Type: In vitro mammalian cell gene mutation test
Method: OECD Test Guideline 476
Result: negative

Test Type: Bacterial reverse mutation assay (AMES)
Method: OECD Test Guideline 471
Result: negative

Test Type: Chromosome aberration test in vitro
Method: OECD Test Guideline 473
Result: negative

1,4-Naphthoquinone:

Genotoxicity in vitro :

Test Type: In vitro mammalian cell gene mutation test
Result: negative

Test Type: Chromosome aberration test in vitro
Method: OECD Test Guideline 473
Result: positive

Genotoxicity in vivo : Test Type: Mutagenicity (in vivo mammalian bone-marrow

SAFETY DATA SHEET

according to Regulation (EC) No. 1907/2006

ANCORANTE CHIMICO WIT-PM 200 -420ML (A)

Version	Revision Date:	SDS Number:	Date of last issue: 21.09.2021
11.1	05.05.2022	10676963-00008	Date of first issue: 14.10.2013

cytogenetic test, chromosomal analysis)
Species: Hamster
Application Route: Ingestion
Method: OECD Test Guideline 475
Result: negative

Carcinogenicity

Not classified based on available information.

Components:

Vinyltoluene:

Species : Rat
Application Route : inhalation (vapour)
Exposure time : 103 weeks
Result : negative

Species : Rat
Application Route : Ingestion
Exposure time : 108 weeks
Result : negative

Methacrylic acid, monoester with propane-1,2-diol:

Species : Rat
Application Route : Inhalation
Exposure time : 102 weeks
Result : negative

Reproductive toxicity

Not classified based on available information.

Components:

Tetramethylene dimethacrylate:

Effects on fertility : Test Type: Combined repeated dose toxicity study with the reproduction/developmental toxicity screening test
Species: Rat
Application Route: Ingestion
Method: OECD Test Guideline 422
Result: negative

Effects on foetal development : Test Type: Combined repeated dose toxicity study with the reproduction/developmental toxicity screening test
Species: Rat
Application Route: Ingestion
Method: OECD Test Guideline 422
Result: negative

Vinyltoluene:

Effects on fertility : Test Type: Two-generation reproduction toxicity study
Species: Rat

SAFETY DATA SHEET

according to Regulation (EC) No. 1907/2006

ANCORANTE CHIMICO WIT-PM 200 -420ML

(A)

Version 11.1 Revision Date: 05.05.2022 SDS Number: 10676963-00008 Date of last issue: 21.09.2021
Date of first issue: 14.10.2013

Application Route: Ingestion
Result: negative
Remarks: Based on data from similar materials

Effects on foetal development : Test Type: Embryo-foetal development
Species: Rat
Application Route: Ingestion
Result: negative
Remarks: Based on data from similar materials

Ethylene dimethacrylate:

Effects on fertility : Test Type: Combined repeated dose toxicity study with the reproduction/developmental toxicity screening test
Species: Rat
Application Route: Ingestion
Method: OECD Test Guideline 422
Result: negative
Remarks: Based on data from similar materials

Effects on foetal development : Test Type: Embryo-foetal development
Species: Rat
Application Route: Ingestion
Method: OECD Test Guideline 414
Result: negative

Methacrylic acid, monoester with propane-1,2-diol:

Effects on fertility : Test Type: Reproduction/Developmental toxicity screening test
Species: Rat
Application Route: Ingestion
Method: OECD Test Guideline 422
Result: negative

Effects on foetal development : Test Type: Embryo-foetal development
Species: Rabbit
Application Route: Ingestion
Method: OECD Test Guideline 414
Result: negative

2,2'-[(4-Methylphenyl)imino]bisethanol:

Effects on foetal development : Test Type: Embryo-foetal development
Species: Rat
Application Route: Ingestion
Method: OECD Test Guideline 414
Result: negative
Remarks: Based on data from similar materials

Reaction mass of 2-[[2-(2-hydroxyethoxy)ethyl](4-methylphenyl)amino]ethanol and 2,2'-[(4-methylphenyl)imino]diethanol:

Effects on foetal development : Test Type: Embryo-foetal development

SAFETY DATA SHEET

according to Regulation (EC) No. 1907/2006

ANCORANTE CHIMICO WIT-PM 200 -420ML (A)

Version	Revision Date:	SDS Number:	Date of last issue: 21.09.2021
11.1	05.05.2022	10676963-00008	Date of first issue: 14.10.2013

ment

Species: Rat
Application Route: Ingestion
Method: OECD Test Guideline 414
Result: negative

1,1'-(p-tolylimino)dipropan-2-ol:

Effects on fertility : Test Type: Combined repeated dose toxicity study with the reproduction/developmental toxicity screening test
Species: Rat
Application Route: Ingestion
Method: OECD Test Guideline 422
Result: negative

Effects on foetal development : Test Type: Combined repeated dose toxicity study with the reproduction/developmental toxicity screening test
Species: Rat
Application Route: Ingestion
Method: OECD Test Guideline 422
Result: negative

1,4-Naphthoquinone:

Effects on fertility : Test Type: Combined repeated dose toxicity study with the reproduction/developmental toxicity screening test
Species: Rat
Application Route: Ingestion
Method: OECD Test Guideline 422
Result: negative

Effects on foetal development : Test Type: Combined repeated dose toxicity study with the reproduction/developmental toxicity screening test
Species: Rat
Application Route: Ingestion
Method: OECD Test Guideline 422
Result: negative

STOT - single exposure

Not classified based on available information.

Components:

Vinyltoluene:

Assessment : May cause respiratory irritation.

Ethylene dimethacrylate:

Assessment : May cause respiratory irritation.

1,4-Naphthoquinone:

Assessment : May cause respiratory irritation.

SAFETY DATA SHEET

according to Regulation (EC) No. 1907/2006

ANCORANTE CHIMICO WIT-PM 200 -420ML

(A)

Version 11.1 Revision Date: 05.05.2022 SDS Number: 10676963-00008 Date of last issue: 21.09.2021
Date of first issue: 14.10.2013

STOT - repeated exposure

Not classified based on available information.

Components:

Ehylene dimethacrylate:

Assessment : No significant health effects observed in animals at concentrations of 1 mg/l/6h/d or less.

2,2'-[(4-Methylphenyl)imino]bisethanol:

Assessment : No significant health effects observed in animals at concentrations of 100 mg/kg bw or less.

Repeated dose toxicity

Components:

Tetramethylene dimethacrylate:

Species : Rat
NOAEL : 300 mg/kg
Application Route : Ingestion
Exposure time : 33 Days
Method : OECD Test Guideline 422

Ehylene dimethacrylate:

Species : Rat, male
NOAEL : 100 mg/kg
LOAEL : 300 mg/kg
Application Route : Ingestion
Exposure time : 50 Days
Method : OECD Test Guideline 422
Remarks : Based on data from similar materials

Species : Rat
LOAEL : 1,23 mg/l
Application Route : inhalation (vapour)
Exposure time : 90 Days
Method : OECD Test Guideline 413

Methacrylic acid, monoester with propane-1,2-diol:

Species : Rat
NOAEL : >= 300 mg/kg
Application Route : Ingestion
Exposure time : 49 Days
Method : OECD Test Guideline 422

2,2'-[(4-Methylphenyl)imino]bisethanol:

Species : Rat
NOAEL : > 30 - 300 mg/kg

SAFETY DATA SHEET

according to Regulation (EC) No. 1907/2006

ANCORANTE CHIMICO WIT-PM 200 -420ML

(A)

Version	Revision Date:	SDS Number:	Date of last issue: 21.09.2021
11.1	05.05.2022	10676963-00008	Date of first issue: 14.10.2013

Application Route : Ingestion
Exposure time : 28 Days
Method : OECD Test Guideline 407
Remarks : Based on data from similar materials

Reaction mass of 2-[[2-(2-hydroxyethoxy)ethyl](4-methylphenyl)amino]ethanol and 2,2'-[[4-methylphenyl]imino]diethanol:

Species : Rat, female
NOAEL : 100 mg/kg
LOAEL : 300 mg/kg
Application Route : Ingestion
Exposure time : 28 Days
Method : OECD Test Guideline 407

Aspiration toxicity

Not classified based on available information.

Components:

Vinyltoluene:

The substance or mixture is known to cause human aspiration toxicity hazards or has to be regarded as if it causes a human aspiration toxicity hazard.

11.2 Information on other hazards

Endocrine disrupting properties

Product:

Assessment : The substance/mixture does not contain components considered to have endocrine disrupting properties according to REACH Article 57(f) or Commission Delegated regulation (EU) 2017/2100 or Commission Regulation (EU) 2018/605 at levels of 0.1% or higher.

SECTION 12: Ecological information

12.1 Toxicity

Components:

Tetramethylene dimethacrylate:

Toxicity to fish : EC50 (Leuciscus idus (Golden orfe)): 32,5 mg/l
Exposure time: 48 h
Method: DIN 38412
Remarks: Based on data from similar materials

Toxicity to algae/aquatic plants : EC10 (Desmodesmus subspicatus (green algae)): 4,35 mg/l
Exposure time: 72 h
Method: OECD Test Guideline 201

SAFETY DATA SHEET

according to Regulation (EC) No. 1907/2006

ANCORANTE CHIMICO WIT-PM 200 -420ML

(A)

Version	Revision Date:	SDS Number:	Date of last issue: 21.09.2021
11.1	05.05.2022	10676963-00008	Date of first issue: 14.10.2013

ErC50 (Desmodesmus subspicatus (green algae)): 9,79 mg/l
Exposure time: 72 h
Method: OECD Test Guideline 201

Toxicity to daphnia and other aquatic invertebrates (Chronic toxicity) : EC10: 7,51 mg/l
Exposure time: 21 d
Species: Daphnia magna (Water flea)
Method: OECD Test Guideline 211

Vinyltoluene:

Toxicity to fish : LC50 (Pimephales promelas (fathead minnow)): > 1 - 10 mg/l
Exposure time: 96 h
Method: OECD Test Guideline 203

Toxicity to daphnia and other aquatic invertebrates : EC50 (Daphnia magna (Water flea)): 9,3 mg/l
Exposure time: 48 h
Method: OECD Test Guideline 202

Toxicity to algae/aquatic plants : ErC50 (Desmodesmus subspicatus (green algae)): 0,319 mg/l
Exposure time: 72 h
Method: OECD Test Guideline 201

EC10 (Desmodesmus subspicatus (green algae)): 0,25 mg/l
Exposure time: 72 h
Method: OECD Test Guideline 201

M-Factor (Acute aquatic toxicity) : 1

Toxicity to microorganisms : NOEC : 170 mg/l
Exposure time: 3 h

Ethylene dimethacrylate:

Toxicity to fish : LC50 (Danio rerio (zebra fish)): 15,95 mg/l
Exposure time: 96 h
Method: OECD Test Guideline 203

Toxicity to daphnia and other aquatic invertebrates : EC50 (Daphnia magna (Water flea)): 44,9 mg/l
Exposure time: 48 h
Method: OECD Test Guideline 202

Toxicity to algae/aquatic plants : EC50 (Pseudokirchneriella subcapitata (green algae)): 17,3 mg/l
Exposure time: 72 h
Method: OECD Test Guideline 201

EC10 (Pseudokirchneriella subcapitata (green algae)): 6,93 mg/l
Exposure time: 72 h
Method: OECD Test Guideline 201

SAFETY DATA SHEET

according to Regulation (EC) No. 1907/2006

ANCORANTE CHIMICO WIT-PM 200 -420ML

(A)

Version	Revision Date:	SDS Number:	Date of last issue: 21.09.2021
11.1	05.05.2022	10676963-00008	Date of first issue: 14.10.2013

Toxicity to microorganisms : EC50 : 570 mg/l
Exposure time: 30 min
Method: ISO 8192

Toxicity to daphnia and other aquatic invertebrates (Chronic toxicity) : NOEC: 5,05 mg/l
Exposure time: 21 d
Species: Daphnia magna (Water flea)
Method: OECD Test Guideline 211

Methacrylic acid, monoester with propane-1,2-diol:

Toxicity to fish : LC50 (Leuciscus idus (Golden orfe)): 493 mg/l
Exposure time: 48 h
Method: DIN 38412

Toxicity to daphnia and other aquatic invertebrates : EC50 (Daphnia magna (Water flea)): > 143 mg/l
Exposure time: 48 h
Method: OECD Test Guideline 202

Toxicity to algae/aquatic plants : ErC50 (Pseudokirchneriella subcapitata (green algae)): > 97,2 mg/l
Exposure time: 72 h
Method: OECD Test Guideline 201

NOEC (Pseudokirchneriella subcapitata (green algae)): >= 97,2 mg/l
Exposure time: 72 h
Method: OECD Test Guideline 201

Toxicity to microorganisms : EC10 (Pseudomonas putida): 1.140 mg/l

Toxicity to daphnia and other aquatic invertebrates (Chronic toxicity) : NOEC: 45,2 mg/l
Exposure time: 21 d
Species: Daphnia magna (Water flea)
Method: OECD Test Guideline 211

2,2'-(4-Methylphenyl)imino]bisethanol:

Toxicity to fish : LC50 (Cyprinus carpio (Carp)): > 100 mg/l
Exposure time: 96 h
Method: OECD Test Guideline 203
Remarks: Based on data from similar materials

Toxicity to daphnia and other aquatic invertebrates : EC50 (Daphnia magna (Water flea)): > 10 - 100 mg/l
Exposure time: 48 h
Method: OECD Test Guideline 202
Remarks: Based on data from similar materials

Toxicity to algae/aquatic plants : ErC50 (Pseudokirchneriella subcapitata (green algae)): > 100 mg/l
Exposure time: 72 h
Method: OECD Test Guideline 201
Remarks: Based on data from similar materials

SAFETY DATA SHEET

according to Regulation (EC) No. 1907/2006

ANCORANTE CHIMICO WIT-PM 200 -420ML

(A)

Version	Revision Date:	SDS Number:	Date of last issue: 21.09.2021
11.1	05.05.2022	10676963-00008	Date of first issue: 14.10.2013

NOEC (Pseudokirchneriella subcapitata (green algae)): > 1 mg/l

Exposure time: 72 h

Method: OECD Test Guideline 201

Remarks: Based on data from similar materials

Toxicity to microorganisms : EC50 (activated sludge): > 100 mg/l
Exposure time: 3 h
Method: OECD Test Guideline 209
Remarks: Based on data from similar materials

Reaction mass of 2-[[2-(2-hydroxyethoxy)ethyl](4-methylphenyl)amino]ethanol and 2,2'-(4-methylphenyl)imino]diethanol:

Toxicity to fish : LC50 (Cyprinus carpio (Carp)): > 100 mg/l
Exposure time: 96 h
Method: OECD Test Guideline 203

Toxicity to daphnia and other aquatic invertebrates : EC50 (Daphnia magna (Water flea)): 48 mg/l
Exposure time: 48 h
Method: OECD Test Guideline 202

Toxicity to algae/aquatic plants : ErC50 (Pseudokirchneriella subcapitata (green algae)): > 100 mg/l
Exposure time: 72 h
Method: OECD Test Guideline 201

NOEC (Pseudokirchneriella subcapitata (green algae)): 100 mg/l

Exposure time: 72 h

Method: OECD Test Guideline 201

Toxicity to microorganisms : EC50 (activated sludge): > 1.000 mg/l
Exposure time: 3 h
Method: OECD Test Guideline 209

1,1'-(p-tolylimino)dipropan-2-ol:

Toxicity to fish : LC50 (Danio rerio (zebra fish)): 17 mg/l
Exposure time: 96 h

Toxicity to daphnia and other aquatic invertebrates : EC50 (Daphnia magna (Water flea)): 28,8 mg/l
Exposure time: 48 h
Method: OECD Test Guideline 202

Toxicity to algae/aquatic plants : NOEC (Desmodesmus subspicatus (green algae)): 57,8 mg/l
Exposure time: 72 h
Method: OECD Test Guideline 201

ErC50 (Desmodesmus subspicatus (green algae)): 245 mg/l
Exposure time: 72 h

Method: OECD Test Guideline 201

SAFETY DATA SHEET

according to Regulation (EC) No. 1907/2006

ANCORANTE CHIMICO WIT-PM 200 -420ML

(A)

Version	Revision Date:	SDS Number:	Date of last issue: 21.09.2021
11.1	05.05.2022	10676963-00008	Date of first issue: 14.10.2013

Toxicity to microorganisms : EC10 : > 1.995 mg/l
Exposure time: 30 min

1,4-Naphthoquinone:

Toxicity to fish : LC50 (Oryzias latipes (Japanese medaka)): 0,045 mg/l
Exposure time: 96 h
Method: OECD Test Guideline 203

Toxicity to daphnia and other : EC50 (Daphnia magna (Water flea)): 0,026 mg/l
aquatic invertebrates : Exposure time: 48 h
Method: OECD Test Guideline 202

Toxicity to algae/aquatic : ErC50 (Pseudokirchneriella subcapitata (green algae)): 0,42
plants : mg/l
Exposure time: 72 h
Method: OECD Test Guideline 201

NOEC (Pseudokirchneriella subcapitata (green algae)): 0,07
mg/l
Exposure time: 72 h
Method: OECD Test Guideline 201

M-Factor (Acute aquatic tox- : 10
icity)

Toxicity to microorganisms : EC10 : 1,28 mg/l
Exposure time: 3 h
Method: OECD Test Guideline 209

M-Factor (Chronic aquatic : 10
toxicity)

12.2 Persistence and degradability

Components:

Tetramethylene dimethacrylate:

Biodegradability : Result: Readily biodegradable.
Biodegradation: 84 %
Exposure time: 28 d
Method: OECD Test Guideline 310

Vinyltoluene:

Biodegradability : Result: Not readily biodegradable.
Biodegradation: 36,7 %
Method: OECD Test Guideline 301D

Ethylene dimethacrylate:

Biodegradability : Result: Readily biodegradable.

SAFETY DATA SHEET

according to Regulation (EC) No. 1907/2006

ANCORANTE CHIMICO WIT-PM 200 -420ML (A)

Version	Revision Date:	SDS Number:	Date of last issue: 21.09.2021
11.1	05.05.2022	10676963-00008	Date of first issue: 14.10.2013

Biodegradation: 71,6 %
Exposure time: 30 d
Method: OECD Test Guideline 301C

Methacrylic acid, monoester with propane-1,2-diol:

Biodegradability : Result: Readily biodegradable.
Biodegradation: 81 %
Exposure time: 28 d
Method: OECD Test Guideline 301C

2,2'-[(4-Methylphenyl)imino]bisethanol:

Biodegradability : Result: Not readily biodegradable.
Method: OECD Test Guideline 301B
Remarks: Based on data from similar materials

Reaction mass of 2-[[2-(2-hydroxyethoxy)ethyl](4-methylphenyl)amino]ethanol and 2,2'-[(4-methylphenyl)imino]diethanol:

Biodegradability : Result: Not readily biodegradable.
Biodegradation: 1,5 %
Exposure time: 29 d
Method: OECD Test Guideline 301B

1,1'-(p-tolylimino)dipropan-2-ol:

Biodegradability : Result: Inherently biodegradable.
Biodegradation: 90,1 %
Exposure time: 60 d
Method: OECD Test Guideline 301B

1,4-Naphthoquinone:

Biodegradability : Result: Not readily biodegradable.
Biodegradation: 0 %
Exposure time: 28 d
Method: OECD Test Guideline 301F

12.3 Bioaccumulative potential

Components:

Tetramethylene dimethacrylate:

Partition coefficient: n- : log Pow: 3,1
octanol/water

Vinyltoluene:

Bioaccumulation : Species: Lepomis macrochirus (Bluegill sunfish)
Bioconcentration factor (BCF): < 500
Remarks: Based on data from similar materials

Partition coefficient: n- : log Pow: 3,44

SAFETY DATA SHEET

according to Regulation (EC) No. 1907/2006

ANCORANTE CHIMICO WIT-PM 200 -420ML (A)

Version 11.1 Revision Date: 05.05.2022 SDS Number: 10676963-00008 Date of last issue: 21.09.2021
Date of first issue: 14.10.2013

octanol/water Remarks: Calculation

Ethylene dimethacrylate:

Partition coefficient: n-octanol/water : log Pow: 2,4

Methacrylic acid, monoester with propane-1,2-diol:

Partition coefficient: n-octanol/water : log Pow: 0,97

2,2'-(4-Methylphenyl)imino]bisethanol:

Partition coefficient: n-octanol/water : log Pow: 2
Method: OECD Test Guideline 117

Reaction mass of 2-[[2-(2-hydroxyethoxy)ethyl](4-methylphenyl)amino]ethanol and 2,2'-[[4-methylphenyl)imino]diethanol:

Partition coefficient: n-octanol/water : log Pow: 2,17
Method: OECD Test Guideline 117

1,1'-(p-tolylimino)dipropan-2-ol:

Partition coefficient: n-octanol/water : log Pow: 2,1

1,4-Naphthoquinone:

Partition coefficient: n-octanol/water : log Pow: 1,77
Method: OECD Test Guideline 107

12.4 Mobility in soil

No data available

12.5 Results of PBT and vPvB assessment

Product:

Assessment : This substance/mixture contains no components considered to be either persistent, bioaccumulative and toxic (PBT), or very persistent and very bioaccumulative (vPvB) at levels of 0.1% or higher.

12.6 Endocrine disrupting properties

Product:

Assessment : The substance/mixture does not contain components considered to have endocrine disrupting properties according to REACH Article 57(f) or Commission Delegated regulation (EU) 2017/2100 or Commission Regulation (EU) 2018/605 at levels of 0.1% or higher.

SAFETY DATA SHEET

according to Regulation (EC) No. 1907/2006

ANCORANTE CHIMICO WIT-PM 200 -420ML (A)

Version	Revision Date:	SDS Number:	Date of last issue: 21.09.2021
11.1	05.05.2022	10676963-00008	Date of first issue: 14.10.2013

12.7 Other adverse effects

No data available

SECTION 13: Disposal considerations

13.1 Waste treatment methods

- Product : Dispose of in accordance with local regulations.
According to the European Waste Catalogue, Waste Codes are not product specific, but application specific.
Waste codes should be assigned by the user, preferably in discussion with the waste disposal authorities.
- Contaminated packaging : Empty containers should be taken to an approved waste handling site for recycling or disposal.
If not otherwise specified: Dispose of as unused product.
- Waste Code : The following Waste Codes are only suggestions:
- used product
08 04 09, waste adhesives and sealants containing organic solvents or other hazardous substances
 - unused product
08 04 09, waste adhesives and sealants containing organic solvents or other hazardous substances
 - uncleaned packagings
15 01 10, packaging containing residues of or contaminated by hazardous substances
-

SECTION 14: Transport information

14.1 UN number or ID number

Not regulated as a dangerous good

14.2 UN proper shipping name

Not regulated as a dangerous good

14.3 Transport hazard class(es)

Not regulated as a dangerous good

14.4 Packing group

Not regulated as a dangerous good

14.5 Environmental hazards

Not regulated as a dangerous good

14.6 Special precautions for user

Not applicable

14.7 Maritime transport in bulk according to IMO instruments

SAFETY DATA SHEET

according to Regulation (EC) No. 1907/2006

ANCORANTE CHIMICO WIT-PM 200 -420ML

(A)

Version	Revision Date:	SDS Number:	Date of last issue: 21.09.2021
11.1	05.05.2022	10676963-00008	Date of first issue: 14.10.2013

Remarks : Not applicable for product as supplied.

SECTION 15: Regulatory information

15.1 Safety, health and environmental regulations/legislation specific for the substance or mixture

REACH - Restrictions on the manufacture, placing on the market and use of certain dangerous substances, mixtures and articles (Annex XVII) : Not applicable

REACH - Candidate List of Substances of Very High Concern for Authorisation (Article 59). : Not applicable

Regulation (EC) No 1005/2009 on substances that deplete the ozone layer : Not applicable

Regulation (EU) 2019/1021 on persistent organic pollutants (recast) : Not applicable

Regulation (EC) No 649/2012 of the European Parliament and the Council concerning the export and import of dangerous chemicals : Not applicable

REACH - List of substances subject to authorisation (Annex XIV) : Not applicable

Seveso III: Directive 2012/18/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council on the control of major-accident hazards involving dangerous substances.
Not applicable

Volatile organic compounds : Directive 2010/75/EU of 24 November 2010 on industrial emissions (integrated pollution prevention and control)
Volatile organic compounds (VOC) content: 2,8 %

Other regulations:

Take note of Directive 94/33/EC on the protection of young people at work or stricter national regulations, where applicable.

Legislative Decree April 9, 2008, 81 (Implementation of Article 1 of the Law of 3 August 2007, n. 123, concerning the protection of health and safety in the workplace.) and subsequent amendments

Legislative Decree April 3, 2006, n. 152, (Environmental standards) and subsequent amendments

Legislative Decree February 6, 2009, 21 (Regulations for the execution of the provisions laid down in Regulation (EC) no. 648/2004 on detergents)

15.2 Chemical safety assessment

A Chemical Safety Assessment has not been carried out.

SECTION 16: Other information

SAFETY DATA SHEET

according to Regulation (EC) No. 1907/2006

ANCORANTE CHIMICO WIT-PM 200 -420ML

(A)

Version	Revision Date:	SDS Number:	Date of last issue: 21.09.2021
11.1	05.05.2022	10676963-00008	Date of first issue: 14.10.2013

Other information : Items where changes have been made to the previous version are highlighted in the body of this document by two vertical lines.

Full text of H-Statements

H226 : Flammable liquid and vapour.
H300 : Fatal if swallowed.
H301 : Toxic if swallowed.
H302 : Harmful if swallowed.
H304 : May be fatal if swallowed and enters airways.
H314 : Causes severe skin burns and eye damage.
H315 : Causes skin irritation.
H317 : May cause an allergic skin reaction.
H318 : Causes serious eye damage.
H319 : Causes serious eye irritation.
H330 : Fatal if inhaled.
H332 : Harmful if inhaled.
H335 : May cause respiratory irritation.
H400 : Very toxic to aquatic life.
H410 : Very toxic to aquatic life with long lasting effects.
H411 : Toxic to aquatic life with long lasting effects.
H412 : Harmful to aquatic life with long lasting effects.

Full text of other abbreviations

Acute Tox. : Acute toxicity
Aquatic Acute : Short-term (acute) aquatic hazard
Aquatic Chronic : Long-term (chronic) aquatic hazard
Asp. Tox. : Aspiration hazard
Eye Dam. : Serious eye damage
Eye Irrit. : Eye irritation
Flam. Liq. : Flammable liquids
Skin Corr. : Skin corrosion
Skin Irrit. : Skin irritation
Skin Sens. : Skin sensitisation
STOT SE : Specific target organ toxicity - single exposure
ACGIH : USA. ACGIH Threshold Limit Values (TLV)
ACGIH / TWA : 8-hour, time-weighted average
ACGIH / STEL : Short-term exposure limit

ADN - European Agreement concerning the International Carriage of Dangerous Goods by Inland Waterways; ADR - Agreement concerning the International Carriage of Dangerous Goods by Road; AIIC - Australian Inventory of Industrial Chemicals; ASTM - American Society for the Testing of Materials; bw - Body weight; CLP - Classification Labelling Packaging Regulation; Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008; CMR - Carcinogen, Mutagen or Reproductive Toxicant; DIN - Standard of the German Institute for Standardisation; DSL - Domestic Substances List (Canada); ECHA - European Chemicals Agency; EC-Number - European Community number; ECx - Concentration associated with x% response; ELx - Loading rate associated with x% response; EmS - Emergency Schedule; ENCS - Existing and New Chemical Substances (Japan); ErCx - Concentration associated with x% growth rate response; GHS - Globally Harmonized System; GLP - Good Laboratory Practice; IARC - International Agency for Research on Cancer; IATA - International Air Transport Association; IBC - International Code for the Construction and Equipment of Ships carrying Dangerous Chemicals in Bulk; IC50 - Half maximal inhibitory concentration; ICAO - Interna-

SAFETY DATA SHEET

according to Regulation (EC) No. 1907/2006

ANCORANTE CHIMICO WIT-PM 200 -420ML

(A)

Version	Revision Date:	SDS Number:	Date of last issue: 21.09.2021
11.1	05.05.2022	10676963-00008	Date of first issue: 14.10.2013

tional Civil Aviation Organization; IECSC - Inventory of Existing Chemical Substances in China; IMDG - International Maritime Dangerous Goods; IMO - International Maritime Organization; ISHL - Industrial Safety and Health Law (Japan); ISO - International Organisation for Standardization; KECI - Korea Existing Chemicals Inventory; LC50 - Lethal Concentration to 50 % of a test population; LD50 - Lethal Dose to 50% of a test population (Median Lethal Dose); MARPOL - International Convention for the Prevention of Pollution from Ships; n.o.s. - Not Otherwise Specified; NO(A)EC - No Observed (Adverse) Effect Concentration; NO(A)EL - No Observed (Adverse) Effect Level; NOELR - No Observable Effect Loading Rate; NZIoC - New Zealand Inventory of Chemicals; OECD - Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development; OPPTS - Office of Chemical Safety and Pollution Prevention; PBT - Persistent, Bioaccumulative and Toxic substance; PICCS - Philippines Inventory of Chemicals and Chemical Substances; (Q)SAR - (Quantitative) Structure Activity Relationship; REACH - Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006 of the European Parliament and of the Council concerning the Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals; RID - Regulations concerning the International Carriage of Dangerous Goods by Rail; SADT - Self-Accelerating Decomposition Temperature; SDS - Safety Data Sheet; SVHC - Substance of Very High Concern; TCSI - Taiwan Chemical Substance Inventory; TECI - Thailand Existing Chemicals Inventory; TRGS - Technical Rule for Hazardous Substances; TSCA - Toxic Substances Control Act (United States); UN - United Nations; vPvB - Very Persistent and Very Bioaccumulative

Further information

Sources of key data used to compile the Safety Data Sheet : Internal technical data, data from raw material SDSs, OECD eChem Portal search results and European Chemicals Agency, <http://echa.europa.eu/>

Classification of the mixture:

Skin Sens. 1	H317
Aquatic Chronic 3	H412

Classification procedure:

Calculation method
Calculation method

The information provided in this Safety Data Sheet is correct to the best of our knowledge, information and belief at the date of its publication. The information is designed only as a guidance for safe handling, use, processing, storage, transportation, disposal and release and shall not be considered a warranty or quality specification of any type. The information provided relates only to the specific material identified at the top of this SDS and may not be valid when the SDS material is used in combination with any other materials or in any process, unless specified in the text. Material users should review the information and recommendations in the specific context of their intended manner of handling, use, processing and storage, including an assessment of the appropriateness of the SDS material in the user's end product, if applicable.

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